

**Madan Bhandari Technological University
Development Board
(MBTU DB)**

Initial University Concept and Curriculum Development Report

Prepared by:

Madan Bhandari Technological University

Development Board

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra

April-2022

Madan Bhandari Technological University

(MBTU)

DECLARATION

I, hereby declare that this study entitled "**Initial University Concept and Curriculum Development Report**" is based on several scholars review and work. I have consulted and prepared it.

Signature:

Prepared by: Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra

Date: April 10, 2022

मदन भण्डारी प्रौद्योगिक विश्वविद्यालय प्रवाधार निर्माण विकास समिति
Madan Bhandari Technological University Development Board

APPROVAL

This is to certify that the report entitled "Initial University Concept and Curriculum Development Report" prepared and submitted by Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, is in accordance of MBTUDB Terms of Reference.

Signature :

Executive Director : Prof. Dr. Binod Aryal

Organization : Madan Bhandari Technological University Development Board

Designation: Executive Director

Date : April, 20, 2022

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Apart from my efforts, the success of this Assignment depends largely on the knowledge, experience, encouragement and guidelines of many others. I take this opportunity to express our gratitude to those people who have been instrumental in the successful completion of this assignment.

I would like to express my greatest appreciation to Prof. Ramchandra Sapkota, Prof. Dr. Bholu Thapa, Prof. Dr. Bhadra Pokhrel, Mr. Guru Baral, Prof. Dr. Sangita Singh, Er. Buddhi Raj Joshi, Prof. Dr. Padma Bahadur Shahi, Mana Raj Kolakshyapati, Ph.D., Mr. Deepak Sharma, Mr. Yamlal Bhusal, Dr. Anil Pokhrel, Prof. Dr. Binod Aryal and Mr. Balkrishn Koirala for their valuable guidance and advice on report which will have a great importance in my professional life. I can't say thank you, enough for their tremendous support and help. I feel motivated and encouraged every time I meet them. Without their encouragement and guidance this assignment would not have materialized.

Lastly, I would also like to give my sincere thanks to all my supporting hands who helped me by providing their valuable input and suggestions for completing comparative report.

Thanking you all

Sincerely,

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra

Table of Content

Introduction	1
Unique Features	2
Unique course specific provisions	3
Vision:"Reaching the Unreached."	3
Objectives	3
Specific Objectives:	3
Bachelor's Degree in Technology (B. Tech.) Draft Curriculum	5
Title of the Course	5
Duration of the Course	5
Credit Requirement for Graduation	6
Educational Philosophy	6
Weightage of the Courses: Comparative Table (for reference only)	6
Course Structure	7
Proposed B. Tech. Course Structure	11
Annex -I	104
Annex-II	109
Annex-III	112

Introduction

Madan Bhandari Technological University (MBTU) is the national priority for the development and advancement of higher education, skill development, vocational education, Research and industrial advancement in Nepal. This also accelerates the enhancement of gross enrolment ratio in the technical higher education sector. The university will be operated as blue ocean competitive strategy as it targets for reaching the unreached through the innovative model of the University provides entry to all, enabling those from both the formal as well as informal systems to acquire education and skills with a view to provide education, training and skill development opportunities to the informal sector and unorganized workforce in order to build productivity also to provide vertical mobility to students undergoing technical, vocational and skill based education and training by offering Diploma, Bachelor, Master and Doctoral programs in high growth sectors and offer various specializations to prepare our youth towards gainful employment. The model has incorporated the strength and best practices of the vocational and skill development system followed in various countries as well as the characteristics of the national ethos and culture. It is to act as national skill Development Corporation of the nation based on industrial need applying action research and publish knowledge and solution through its own publication. It will provide learning, teaching, capacity, capability and skills development and research and development in higher and technical education, covering a wide spectrum of domains and specializations as may be relevant from time to time including, inter-alia, Engineering, Medical, Agricultural ,Natural resources , industrial, Construction etc and their inter-disciplinary studies and development ; for creating higher level of cognitive, affective and psychomotor (head, hearts and hands) abilities and higher levels of intellectual abilities ; It aims to create and deploy new educational programs to promote creativity, innovation and entrepreneurship for inventing of new ways for development and social reconstruction and transformation by establishing the state-of-the-art facilities for education, vocational education, skill training and development through its professional and development services to the industry and public organizations and society. It acts as centers of excellence for research and development in Technology for socio- economic development, and for sharing knowledge and its application. It will use modern and post-modern processes, mechanisms and technologies for governance and management of learning, teaching, researching, evaluating, developing, organizing and creating socioeconomic wealth for individuals and society for the century. It always focus to start higher education programs, courses in new and emerging areas with innovative approaches by establishing links, collaborations and partnerships with other higher education and research institutions in Nepal and abroad. It will pursue any other objectives as may be suggested by the Government.

To provide learning opportunities to wide range of learners representing diverse backgrounds, age groups and socio-economic status and geographic location through a self-paced, self-styled learning environment; it will be operated in all 7 states gradually with specific focus at one location for excellency. Using concept of 'Virtual Campus' where students will come together with experienced faculty and industry members to develop , evolve and university will conduct regular research in labour market requirements in order to understand emerging trends and offer suitable curricula, courses and programs. Assuring council and university Grant Commission norms, it offers facility of credit banking or transfer system to create

options of multi-entry and exit and opportunities, integrated degree and dual degree for movement across Universities or domains or sectors. It will attempt to provide students an opportunity of life long and continuous training through University courses offered through conventional or blended or distance or open or online education and other education delivery models suitable for different pedagogical approaches and systems to trace and enhance performance. It should plan to establish Campuses, Skill Centers, Community Colleges, Study Centers, Information Centers, Test or Examination Centers, Centers of Excellence, Off Campus, Off shore Campuses, etc. at various locations in and outside the country to facilitate delivery, student services and dissemination of education, consultancy, information and skill training.

This university will be solution for developing sustainable economy focusing self-employment, employee in the nation overcoming high foreign deployment and it will also promote local technology and skills covering school drop outs at various levels.

Unique Features

Technology has added manufacturing value resulting increase in per capita which could not make us competitive with only 1.5 % human capital growth rate in average. Based on educational statistics assessment of 2017, The total students who enroll in class 11/12 are 584072 including community school with 427268 and in private school 156786 students. Out of which only 239971 students at rate of 41% appear in the final examination of class 12 with a 49 % pass rate, 117778 students pass which around 20% only of enrollment. Similarly, for class 9/10, enrolment is 970720pass out (34%)-330044 however 640676 cannot achieve successful educational objective. 466294 students struggled during 11/12 but cannot make the set target. In this way, only in 4 years of education 1106970 youth are losing which may cause the nation to be lost. This is why it is urged to establish MBTU for including the excluded also with following attraction.

- Attempt to ensure access of all in Education through formalizing the informal skills.
- Vertical growth of skill based education through integration of Industry and Technology.
- Entry from Diploma, +2 and Informal sector after cognition test
- Cognition test will be conducted at each level.
- Entrepreneurship will be focused.
- Teaching with high industrial exposure
- Virtual campus for continuity of learning bringing industrial expert, academician and researchers among students
- Social Entrepreneurship and incubation center for promotion of business applying action research of demand.
- Skill and knowledge with integrity and ethics
- Students incubation center under guidance of faculty
- Individual research center of faculty including students, industry expert and foreign faculty

- Central university to capture new demands
- Create uncontested market through first technological university.
- to waive courses and duration for the Diploma or similar relevant programs for experienced candidates (up to 1 or 2 semesters) - Lateral Entry of integrated master program in 5 years of dual degrees in different discipline for fulfilling minimum requirements of individual program

Unique course specific provisions

The infrastructure will be developed gradually in all states with head office and Engineering Technology at Kathmandu, Jagdol in the area of 3600 ropani and Study Excellence Center for forestry and Natural resource at Rayale, Kavare in the area of 1651 ropani of Bagmati Province together with Sustainable Himalayan technology operation at Lamachaur, Gandaki Province in the area of 3583 ropani and with same area at Belka, Udayapur of province 1 as excellence center for agriculture technology along with Medical Technology at Urlabari, Morang in the area of 267 ropani.

MBTU shall be different to other academic institutions in that it will integrate the knowledge of conventional technology of farmers, masons, foreman, blacksmith, goldsmith, carpenters and other native people with academic courses, in one side and on the other side; it will promote and upgrade the local technologies blending with modern technology. The research shall be carried out on the real ground. All these research shall be the applied research with solutions to prevailing issues. There will be MoUs with different industries, professional and industrial bodies for technology development, technology transfer, joint research projects and entrepreneurship development.

Vision: "Reaching the Unreached."

The vision of MBTU is to become the first technological university that produces Total Quality Human Capital, technologists and researchers competent and committed for building prosperous Nepal where citizens enjoy a life of greater security, well-being and personal dignity.

Mission: To offer technological, career-directed educational programs focusing on innovative problem-solving research in the field of engineering and technology, and allied sciences with a national identity and international outlook.

Objectives

Overall Objective: The overall objective of the university is to reach the unreached for the development and advancement of higher education, skill development, and vocational education in the country to "Prosperous Nepal, Happy Nepalese"

Specific Objectives:

- To offer competitive technological education with sound theoretical knowledge and practical foundations for producing human capital to meet the needs of society and national development plans,
- To engage in research and development activities to explore meaningful and useful technology to improve productivity and income of enterprises,
- To provide carrier pathways for the graduates of technical and vocational education.

- To minimize the gap of academic knowledge and knowledge at workplace.
- To provide professional and development services to the industry, organizations, agencies and the society at large;
- To upgrade the conventional knowledge and skill prevailing in the workplace to the level of present-day technology through certification and innovation.
- To strengthen the teaching and research on problem-based approach and integrate academic knowledge to production areas, so that the productivity could be enhanced and aspirations of the consumers could be fulfilled.
- To provide Highly qualified and motivated faculties, staffs, competent students, modern infrastructure, new academic programs, research laboratories, innovation and creativity workshops, and other education resources shall be the integral components of the university.
- To assure national development through Technological innovation, employment and wealth creation, improvement of living standards of the people and creation of self-employment opportunities in the country. This will help improve productivity and economy of the nation.
- To collaborate and cooperate between industry and academia for overcoming the issue of employment opportunity of fresh graduates through an exposure to current practices in the industry. Experts from industry shall be appointed as adjunct faculty members and as examiners for students' project evaluation.

Madan Bhandari Technological University
Bachelor's Degree in Technology (B. Tech.)
Draft Curriculum

1. Introduction

Madan Bhandari Technological University will be offering following courses with the objectives of producing high level skilled technical manpower capable of undertaking works in the national, regional and global engineering and technology field. The details of the curriculum shall be as given below:

1.1 Title of the Course

Bachelor/Master in Technology (Construction, Architecture, Information, Mechatronics, Mining and Metallurgy, Livestock and Veterinary, Agriculture, Dairy Technology, Forestry, Medical Technology/Medical Electronics, Food Technology, Public Health, Nursing)

For example;

1. B. Tech. in Construction Technology
2. B.Tech in Mechanical & Automation Engineering (Manufacturing Engineering/Control and instrumentation engineering/ Materials Engineering, Automation, operation)
3. B.Tech. in Mechatronics (mechanical, electrical, telecommunication, control and computer engineering)
4. B.Tech. inLOCAL LEVEL?(civil and rural)
5. B. Tech in Forestry and Wood Technology
6. B. Tech in Agroforestry
7. B. Tech in Agriculture Technology
8. B.Tech. in Livestock and Veterinary Technology
9. B.Tech. in Medical Technology (General, Radiotherapy, Medical Electronics)
10. B. Tech in Clinical Technology (Clinical Research, Tissue Engineering, Animal Facility)
11. B. Tech in Industrial Biotechnology
12. B. Tech in Software Engineering
13. B. Tech. in Urban Development
14. B.Tech. in Mining and Metallurgy
15. B.Tech. in Dairy Technology
16. B.Tech. in Food Technology
17. Bachelor in Nursing and Hospital Management

1.2 Duration of the Course

The total duration of the course will be 4 years plus Internship as applicable. Each year will consist of two semesters, each semester will have 90 working days (15 weeks).

There will be provisions:

- to **waive courses** and duration for the Diploma or similar relevant programs for experienced candidates (up to 1 or 2 semesters) – Lateral Entry of **integrated master** program in 5 years of **dual degrees** in different discipline for fulfilling minimum requirements of individual program

1.3 Credit Requirement for Graduation

Minimum Credit: 144 credits (18cr x 8 semester)

Maximum: 216 credits (27cr x 8 semester)

Definition

1 semester – 15 Working weeks (out of 24 weeks, 6 weeks end semester break, 3 weeks in semester breaks)

1 Cr Theory – 1 hour direct teaching /week

1 Cr Tutorial – 1 hour direct tutoring /week

1 Cr Practical/Project – 3 Hours engagement in Lab/Field //week

Course types

3Cr Theory Course: includes (3 hr lecture + 1 hr tutorial)

3 Cr Course with Practical and project: includes (2 hr lecture + 1 hr tutorial and/or 3 hr practical/project)

It justifies 50% In Semester and 50% End Semester Evaluation **with 25% skill test?**

Educational Philosophy

Minimum Knowledge is prerequisite, which will be acquired through lectures and tutorials. Competency is through: Project Based/ Competency Based/ Skill Based Learning, transferred to credit.

Weightage of the Courses: Comparative Table (for reference only)

Courses Grouping	Indian	IIT	NEC	KU	IOE TU	MBTU
Math and Science (Nat. Sc.)	36 C	20 %	15–25 %	27 Cr (18%)	27 cr	24Cr (15?? %)
Communication skills Humanities	8	20 %	5 – 10 %	13 Cr (~9%)	5 cr	16Cr (10?? %)
Engineering Science	12	20%	15 – 25 %	46 Cr (30%)	65 cr	50 Cr (31?? %)
Engineering Practice	8	10%	5 %	31 Cr (~21%)	31 cr	30 Cr (19?? %)
Engineering Electives	16	10%	~10 %	6 Cr (4 %)	9 cr	9Cr (5?? %)
Departmental Major	-	20%	45 -65 %	27 Cr (18%)	39 cr	32 Cr (20?? %)
Non Credit Course						Traditional Skill will be promoted
				150 cr	176 cr	161 cr

Course Structure

The course is divided into 8 semesters. The first year courses include fundamental subjects. The second and third year generally include specific subjects of the related disciplines. The final year include professional and application type courses.

Information about lecture, tutorial and practical hours per week, full marks and pass marks for internal assessment and final examination, and the duration of final examination of each subject will be given in the course structures of the related program.

Faculty-wise course development guidelines are given in the following sequence:

1. Course Description:
2. Course Objective:
3. General Guidelines:
4. Contents:
5. Evaluation:

Activities Table

Courses	Activities				
	Assignments	Group work	Excursion	Internship	Projects
Basic Science	Chapter wise				
Courses from other department	Chapter wise	Monthly			
Courses from own department			Chapter wise	Yearly	Part wise

1. Tentative Allocated Number of Hours by Years, Parts and Type

Total Marks(Credit)										
Years	First		Second		Third		Fourth		Total	
Parts	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II		
Basic Science (SH)										(15)% ?
Courses from other department										(10-15)% ?
Courses from own department										(70)% ?
Total										100%

2. Course Code

Each subject is specified by a unique code consisting of two letters followed by three-digit number for core courses and five digit numbers for elective courses. The first two letters denote the department which offers the subject (SH: Science and Humanities, AE: Agriculture Engineering, AR: Architecture, EE: Electrical Engineering, ME: Mechanical Engineering, CT: Computer Engineering and so on.

The first digit of the number denotes the year on which the subject is offered (4 for first year, 5 for second year, 6 for third year, and 7 for fourth year respectively for Bachelor's level courses). The remaining two digits 01 to 49 are used for the core subjects offered in odd semester and 51 to 99 are used for the core subjects offered in even semesters. Two extra digits from 01 to 99 are used for the elective courses.

Core Courses:

AB	DEF
----	-----

AB: Offering Department (SH, AE, AR, EE, ME or CT)

D: Year (4 for first year, 5 for second year, 6 for third year and 7 for fourth year)

EF: 01 to 49 for courses offered in odd semesters and 51 to 99 for courses offered in even semester.

Elective Courses:

AB	DEFGH
----	-------

GH: 01 to 99 Specific numbers to each elective course.

For example, ME 651 is the code for the core course “Machine Design” which is offered in third year second part by the Department of Mechanical Engineering.

ME 72505 is code for the elective course “Basics of Micro Hydropower Plant” which is offered in fourth year first part by the Department of Mechanical Engineering.

3 Instruction Methods

The method of teaching is lecture augmented by tutorials and/or practical, whichever is relevant. Tutorials are used to enlarge and develop the topic and concepts stated in the lecture. Practical classes in the form of laboratory works and design/drawing practices are used to verify the concepts and to develop necessary basic skills. Each course is specified with certain lectures, tutorial and practical hours per week. The use of smart teaching will be encouraged for conducting higher level courses.

4 Internal Assessment and Final Examination

The students’ performance in each subject is evaluated by continuous internal assessment and final examination.

4.1 Internal Assessment

50% of the total marks is allocated for internal assessment for theory part of all subjects. Internal assessment mark should include class performance, timely submissions and correctness of assignments, class tests, quizzes and other activities.

Evaluation of practical part of most of the subjects is done through continuous assessment. It includes lab performance, report submission, presentation, viva.

80% attendance is mandatory to qualify for the final examination.

4.2 Final Examination

Final examination of 3 hours for theoretical subjects with full mark of 50 and 1,5 hours for theoretical subject with full mark of 25 will be conducted as per academic calendar of MBTU.

4.3 Pass Marks

Students must obtain 50% marks in both internal assessment and final examination of each subject to pass in the subject. Only students who have passed the internal assessment of a particular subject are allowed to appear in the final examination of that subject.

5. Evaluation System

Students who have passed all the components of all subjects in all semesters are considered to have successfully completed the course. The overall achievement of each student is measured by a final aggregate percentage which is obtained by providing a weight to percentage scored by the students in each semester.

Students Evaluation	General courses	Courses designated as 'practical'
Continuous In-semester assessment	50 percent	75 percent
End-semester examination – theory	50 percent	
End-semester examination - viva or other practical examinations	-	25 percent

The continuous in-semester assessment shall be taken by the concerned course in-charge in any of the following ways:

- | | | |
|--------------------|--------------------|----------------------|
| a. Written test | b. Quizzes | c. Workshop practice |
| d. Practical works | e. Project work | f. Viva-voce |
| g. Open book test | h. Home assignment | i. MCQ |
| j. Field work | k. lab work | l. industrial visit |

For the end-semester examination, the structure of the question paper of all courses other than those designated as 'practical' shall be as follows:

Types of questions	Number of items/questions	Mark for each item/question	Total mark	Duration
Objective test items (multiple choice or fill-in the blank) (memory, analysis, application)				
Short answer questions (memory and application)				
Long answer questions (high application and analytical)				
Total				

Short answer questions shall evaluate the knowledge of the subject matter while long answer question should be of problem solving and critical thinking nature.

Grading Definition and Graduations

Percent of marks	Letter grade	Meaning
80 and above	A	Outstanding
75 and below 80	A-	Excellent

70 and below 75	B+	Very Good
65 and below 70	B	Good
60 and below 65	B-	Fair
55 and below 60	C+	Fair
50 and below 55	C	Fair
45 and below 50	C-	Poor
40 and below 45	D	Poor
Below 40	F	Fail

Grade Point

Grade	A	A-	B+	B	B-	C+	C	C-	D	F
Grade Point	4	3.7	3.3	3	2.7	2.3	2	1.7	1	0

SGPA/CGPA Requirement for Graduation: **2/2.5 (?)**

Depending upon the final weighted aggregate percentage scored by a student a division is awarded as follows:

80% and above	Distinction
65% or above and below 80%	First
50% or above and below 65%	Second

Madan Bhandari Technological University

Proposed B. Tech. Course Structure

1 **Objective:**

2. **General Guidelines:**

Contents:

Control/Coordination:

3. **The Tentative Matrix of Activities**

Courses	Activities				
	Assignments	Colloquium	Excursion	Internship	Projects
Theoretical	Chapter wise				
Technological	Chapter wise	Monthly			
Professional			Chapter wise	Yearly	Part wise

4. **The Tentative Allocated Number of Hours by Years, Parts and Type**

Total Marks(Credit)										
Years	First		Second		Third		Fourth		Total	
Parts	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II		
Basic Science (SH)	500	100	100	100	100				900	(16.5)%
Courses from other department										(16.5)%
Courses from own department										(67)%
Total									5400	100%

Madan Bhandari Technological University
B.Tech. DEGREE
Course Structure, 2021

Year : I										Part : I				
Teaching Schedule							Examination Scheme					Total	Remark (Credit)	
S · N ·	Course Code	Course Title	L	T	P	Total	Theory			Practical				
							Assessm ent Marks	Final		Assessm ent Marks	Final			
								Durati on hours	Mar ks		Durati on hours	Mar ks		
1														
2														
3														
4														
5														
6														
Year : I										Part : II				
Teaching Schedule							Examination Scheme					Total	Remark (Credit)	
S · N ·	Course Code	Course Title	L	T	P	Total	Theory			Practical				
							Assessm ent Marks	Final		Assessm ent Marks	Final			
								Durati on hours	Mar ks		Durati on hours	Mar ks		
1														
2														
3														
4														
5														
6														

Madan Bhandari Technological University

B. Tech. Degree, Major streams for selection of Elective Courses (Example of IoE Civil Engineering)

Stream I: Structure		Stream II: Water Resources		Stream III: Geo-tech./Transportation		Stream: Environmental	
Elective I							
EG661CE	Structural Dynamics	EG664CE	Rock Engineering I	EG667CE	Rock Engineering I	EG671CE	Solid waste Management
EG662CE	Seismic Resistant design of masonry structure	EG665CE	Soil Conservation and watershed Management	EG668CE	Transportation Planning & Engineering	EG672CE	Water And Wastewater Quality Analysis
EG663CE	Design of Suspension Bridge	EG666CE	Geo Hazard	EG669CE	Geo Hazard		
				EG670CE	Ropeway Engineering		
Elective II							
EG711CE	Design of Bridge	EG715CE	Rock Slope Engineering	EG718CE	Rock Slope Engineering	EG723CE	Domestic water and Waste Water Engineering and Management
EG712CE	Geotechnical earthquake Engineering	EG716CE	Hill Irrigation Engineering	EG719CE	Rock Mechanics	EG724CE	Climate Change
EG713CE	Vulnerability assessment and Retrofitting techniques	EG717CE	Ground Water Engineering	EG720CE	Advanced Geo-technical Engineering	EG725CE	Water quality management
EG714CE	Seismic Risk Assessment			EG721CE	Traffic Engineering & Management	EG726CE	Post disaster water and sanitation management
				EG722CE	Rural road Engineering	EG727CE	Public health and risk Assessment
Elective III							
EG761CE	GIS & Remote Sensing	EG761CE	GIS & Remote Sensing	EG761CE	GIS & Remote Sensing	EG761CE	GIS & Remote Sensing
EG762CE	Construction safety Management	EG762CE	Construction safety Management	EG762CE	Construction safety Management	EG762CE	Construction safety Management
EG763CE	Procurement Management	EG763CE	Procurement Management	EG763CE	Procurement Management	EG763CE	Procurement Management
EG764CE	Environmental	EG764CE	Environmental	EG764CE	Environmental	EG764CE	Environmental

	Impact Assessment		Impact Assessment		Impact Assessment		Impact Assessment
EG765CE	Disaster Risk Management						

Appendix A
Bachelor of Technology
Mechanical and Automation Engineering
Offered by
Madan Bhandari Technological University
2021, July
Bachelor of Technology (B. Tech)
Mechanical and Automation Engineering (MAE)

1. Program Objectives

The Bachelor of Technology (B. Tech) in Mechanical and Automation Engineering (MAE) program is designed to produce capable **engineers** who are responsible for the technical management, maintenance and development of new and existing production lines.

- To work to improve the process of making products such as food and drink, plastics and pharmaceuticals.
- to work to add computerized controls to an already existing mechanical system, thus increasing the efficiency and productivity of these machines and lowering the cost of production.
- To enhances the understanding of control systems, information technology, and machinery structures. The students receive knowledge about several concepts such as electronics, thermal science, programming, and electrical machinery, among several others.
- To design, develop and install the devices and systems used in manufacturing facilities and plants.
- To ensure that industrial equipment and machinery work safely and efficiently. They may work in an office, a laboratory, on a factory floor or all three.
- To use their expertise to produce specifications for, design, process and apply materials effectively.
- To give them skill and knowledge on the science and engineering of materials.

Typical job title may be Instructional Designer, Process Engineer, Project Engineer, Automation Engineer, production manager, Materials engineers, Control and instrumentation engineers and many more

Typical responsibilities of the job include may include the following :

- designing new equipment, processes, procedures and systems

- efficiency and productivity of these machines and lowering the cost of production using computerized system
- purchasing and installing equipment
- repairing equipment
- responding to breakdowns
- investigating production problems
- making improvements to current operations to enhance efficiency
- supervising engineering and technical staff
- managing budgets
- maintaining statistical and financial records
- diagnosing faults
- planning and organising maintenance
- liaising with suppliers, customers and research and development staff.
- preparing and agreeing project budgets, timescales and specifications with clients and managers
- undertaking relevant research
- producing and implementing designs
- creating test procedures
- testing, evaluating, modifying and calibrating products and instruments
- writing reports and documentation
- analysing and interpreting data
- collaborating with a team of scientists and engineers
- providing technical support.
- developing, modifying, testing and evaluating materials
- providing technical advice about the suitability of materials
- diagnosing faults
- advising on, planning and organising inspections, maintenance and repairs
- overseeing operational quality control processes
- supervising engineering and technical staff

Key skills for MAE engineers

- Sound scientific and technical knowledge
- Commercial awareness
- The ability to work well under pressure
- Problem-solving skills
- Team working skills
- Relevant technical knowledge
- IT skills

- Analytical skills.
- Confidence
- Leadership skills
- Effective organisational skills
- Communication and interpersonal skills

Shift and 'on-call' work may be required, particularly where manufacturing equipment is in continual 24-hour operation. Career progression often happens through moves into managerial positions or related areas of employment such as plant/production engineering.

Madan Bhandari Technological University
Bachelor of Technology
(Similar to all Branches)

FIRST SEMESTER EXAMINATION

Code No.	Paper ID	Paper	L	T/P	Credits	Status
THEORY PAPERS						
		Applied Mathematics-I	3	1	4	M
		Applied Physics-I	2	1	3	M
		Manufacturing Processes(Specific)	3	0	3	M
		Electrical Technology	3	0	3	M
		Human Values and Professional Ethics-	1	1	1	--
		Fundamentals of Computing	2	0	2	--
		Applied Chemistry	2	1	3	M
PRACTICAL/VIVA VOCE						
		Applied Physics Lab-I	-----	2	1	
		Electrical Technology Lab	-----	2	1	M
		Workshop Practice	-----	3	2	M
		Engineering Graphics Lab	-----	3	2	
		Fundamentals of Computing Lab	-----	2	1	--
		Applied Chemistry Lab	-----	2	1	--
		NCC/NSS*#	-----	-----	-----	--
TOTAL			16	18	27	

M: Mandatory for award of degree

#NUES (Non University Examination System)

*#NCC/NSS can be completed in any one semester from Semester 1 – Semester 4. It will be evaluated internally by the respective institute. The credit for this will be given after fourth Semester. The camps/classes will be held either during Weekends/Holidays or Winter/Summer Vacations.

Madan Bhandari Technological University

Bachelor of Technology (Similar to all Branches) Second Semester Examination

Code No.	Paper ID	Paper	L	T/P	Credits	Status
THEORY PAPERS						
ETMA-102		Applied Mathematics-II	3	1	4	M
ETPH-104		Applied Physics-II	2	1	3	
ETEC-106		Electronic Devices	3	0	3	M
ETCS-108		Introduction to Programming	3	0	3	M
ETME-110		Engineering Mechanics	2	1	3	--
ETHS-112		Communication Skills	2	1	3	--
ETEN-114		Environmental Studies	2	1	3	--
PRACTICAL/VIVA VOCE						
ETPH-152		Applied Physics Lab-II	-----	2	1	
ETCS-154		Programming Lab	-----	2	1	M
ETEC-156		Electronic Devices Lab	-----	2	1	M
ETME-158		Engineering Mechanics Lab	-----	2	1	--
ETEN-160		Environmental Studies Lab	-----	2	1	--
		NCC/NSS*#	-----	-----	-----	--
TOTAL			17	15	27	

M: Mandatory for award of degree

#NUES (Non University Examination System)

*#NCC/NSS can be completed in any one semester from Semester 1 – Semester 4. It will be evaluated internally by the respective institute. The credit for this will be given after fourth Semester.

Madan Bhandari Technological University
Bachelor of Technology
(Mechanical and Automation Engineering)

Third semester Examination

Code No.	Paper ID	Paper	L	T/P	Credits	Status
THEORY PAPERS						
ETME-201		Fluid Mechanics	3	1	4	M
ETME-203		Thermal Science	3	1	4	M
ETAT-203		Strength of Material	3	1	4	M
ETME-205		Production Technology	3	1	4	M
ETME-207		Material Science and Metallurgy	3	0	3	
ETME-209		Electrical Machines	3	0	3	
PRACTICAL/VIVA VOCE						
ETME-251		Fluid Mechanics Lab	0	2	1	
ETAT-257		Strength of Material Lab	0	2	1	
ETTE-259		Machine Drawing Lab	0	3	2	
ETME-253		Electrical Machines Lab	0	2	1	
		NCC/NSS*	-----	-----	-----	
TOTAL			18	13	27	

M: Mandatory for the award of degree.

*NCC/NSS can be completed in any one semester from Semester 1 – Semester 4. It will be evaluated internally by the respective institute. The credit for this will be given after fourth Semester.

Madan Bhandari Technological University
Bachelor of Technology (Mechanical and Automation Engineering)
Fourth Semester Examination

Code No.	Paper ID	Paper	L	T/P	Credits	Status
THEORY PAPERS						
ETMA-202		Numerical Analysis and Statistical Techniques	3	1	4	
ETAT-204		Fluid Systems	3	1	4	
ETAT-202		Theory of Machines	3	1	4	M
ETME-206		Manufacturing Machines	3	1	4	M
ETME-208		Measurements and Instrumentation	3	0	3	
ETEC-202		Switching Theory and Logic Design	3	0	3	M
PRACTICAL/VIVA VOCE						
ETMA-252		Numerical Analysis and Statistical Techniques Lab	-----	2	1	
ETAT-254		Fluid Systems Lab	-----	2	1	
ETAT-252		Theory of Machines Lab	-----	2	1	
ETME-256		Manufacturing Machines Lab	-----	2	1	
ETEC-252		Switching Theory and Logic Design Lab	-----	2	1	
ETSS-250		NCC/NSS*	-----	-----	1	
TOTAL			18	14	28	

M: Mandatory for the award of degree.

*NCC/NSS can be completed in any one semester from Semester 1 – Semester 4. It will be evaluated internally by respective institute. The credit for this will be given after fourth Semester.

NOTE: 4 weeks Industrial / In-house Workshop will be held after fourth semester. However, Viva-Voce will be conducted in the fifth semester.

Madan Bhandari Technological University
Bachelor of Technology
(Mechanical and Automation Engineering)

Fifth Semester Examination

Code No.	Paper ID	Paper	L	T/P	Credits	Status
THEORY PAPERS						
ETME-301		Management of Manufacturing Systems	3	0	3	
ETAT-303		Metal Cutting and Tool Design	3	1	4	M
ETAT-305		Heat Transfer and I.C. Engines	3	1	4	M
ETAT-307		Metrology	3	0	3	M
ETEL-307		Control Systems	3	1	4	
ETHS-301		Communication Skills for Professionals	2	0	1	
PRACTICAL/VIVA VOCE						
ETAT-351		Metal cutting and Tool Design Lab	0	2	1	
ETAT-353		Heat Transfer and I.C. Engine lab	0	2	1	
ETAT-355		Metrology lab	0	2	1	
ETEL-355		Control Systems Lab	0	2	1	
ETHS-351		Communication Skills for Professionals Lab	0	2	1	

ETAT-357		Industrial Training (conducted after	0	0	1	
		fourth semester of 4-6 weeks)				
		Total	17	13	25	

M: Mandatory for the award of degree.

*Viva-Voce for evaluation of Industrial Training / In-house Workshop will be conducted in this semester.

Note: Minimum of 2 weeks of In-house training related to ME will be held after 5th semester; however, viva-voce will be conducted in 6th Semester (ETAT 362).

Madan Bhandari Technological University
BACHELOR OF TECHNOLOGY

		(MECHANICAL AND AUTOMATION ENGINEERING)					
		SIXTH SEMESTER EXAMINATION					
Code No.	Paper ID	Paper	L	T/P	Credits	Status	
THEORY PAPERS							
ETAT-302		Machine Design	3	1	4	M	
ETAT-304		Automobile Engineering	3	0	3		
ETEC-310		Data Communications and Networks	3	1	4		
ETAT-306		Operations Research	3	1	4		
ETME-308		Refrigeration and Air Conditioning	3	1	4	M	
ETEE-310		Microprocessors and Microcontrollers	3	1	4	M	
PRACTICAL/VIVA VOCE							
ETAT-352		Machine Design Lab	0	2	1		
ETAT-354		Automobile Engg Lab	0	2	1		

ETEC- 358		Data Communications and Networks Lab	0	2	1	
ETME-358		Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Lab	0	2	1	
ETEE-358		Microprocessor and Microcontroller Lab	0	2	1	
ETAT-362		In-house training (two weeks)	0	0	1	
TOTAL			18	15	29	

M: Mandatory for award of degree

Note: Minimum of 4-6 weeks of industrial training related to MAE will be held after 6th semester; however, viva-voce will be conducted in 7th Semester (ETAT-459).

Imp:- Elective Paper will be floated in 7th Semester, if one-third of the total students opt for the same. It is advised that the decision about the elective subject for 7th Semester is done before the end of 6th semester.

BACHELOR OF TECHNOLOGY					
(MECHANICAL AND AUTOMATION ENGINEERING)					
SEVENTH SEMESTER EXAMINATION					
Code No.	Paper ID	Paper	L	T/P	Credits
THEORY PAPERS					
ETAT-401		Computer Aided Design	3	1	4
ETME-403		Computer Integrated Manufacturing	3	1	4
ETAT-403		Mechatronics	3	0	3
Elective-I (choose any one)					
ETME-407		Optimization Techniques	3	0	3
ETME-409		Preventive Maintenance and Condition Monitoring	3	0	3
ETME-411		Computational Fluid Dynamics	3	0	3

ETME-423		Finite Element Methods	3	0	3
ETEE-419		Renewable Energy Resources	3	0	3
ETCS-429		Artificial Intelligence	3	0	3
ETCS-425		Database Management System	3	0	3
Elective-II (Choose any one)					
ETME-417		Advanced material science and metallurgy	3	0	3
ETEE-403		Advanced Control System	3	0	3
ETME-405		Power Plant Engineering	3	0	3
ETCS-411		Introduction to Data Science	3	0	3
ETME-421		Management Information System and ERP	3	0	3
ETAT-407		Advanced Manufacturing Methods	3	0	3
ETHS-419		Sociology and Elements of Indian History for Engineers	3	0	3
PRACTICAL/VIVA VOCE					
ETAT-451		Computer Aided Design Lab	0	2	1
ETME-453		Computer Integrated Manufacturing Lab	0	2	1
ETAT-453		Mechatronics Lab	0	2	1
ETAT-455		Lab Based on Elective- I or II	0	2	1
ETAT-457		Minor Project+	0	6	3
ETAT-459		Summer training#	0	0	1
TOTAL			15	16	25

Imp:-Elective Paper will be floated if one-third of the total students opt for the same. It is advised that the decision about the elective subject for 8th Semester is done before the end of

seventh semester. New Electives may be added as per requirement after getting it duly approved by CDC and Deanrespectively.

The student will submit a synopsis at the beginning of the semester for approval from the departmental committee in a specified format, thereafter he/she will have to present the progress of the work through seminars and progress reports.

#NUES (Non University Examination System)

					9
		BACHELOR OF TECHNOLOGY			
		(MECHANICAL AND AUTOMATION ENGINEERING)			
		EIGHTH SEMESTER EXAMINATION			
Code No.	Paper ID	Paper	L	T/P	Credits
ETMT-402		Robotics	3	1	4
ETME-402		Engineering System Modelling and Simulation	3	1	4
ETHS-402		Human Values and Professional Ethics-II	1	0	1
Elective-III (choose any one)					
ETEC-432		Image Processing and Machine Vision	3	0	3
ETIT-410		Soft Computing	3	0	3
ETME-426		Total Quality Management	3	0	3
ETME-414		Applied Plasticity	3	0	3
ETME-430		Computer Aided Graphics and Product design	3	0	3
ETEC-434		Microprocessor System Based Process Design	3	0	3
Elective-IV(choose any one)					
ETAT-432		Gas Turbines and Compressors	3	0	3
ETME-424		Cryogenic Engineering	3	0	3
ETME-412		Rapid Prototyping	3	0	3
ETMT-428		Flexible Manufacturing System	3	0	3

ETTE-424		Supply Chain management-planning	3	0	3
ETAT-442		Process Planning and Cost Estimation	3	0	3
PRACTICAL/VIVA VOCE					
ETMT-452		Robotics Lab	0	2	1
ETME-452		Engineering System Modelling and Simulation Lab	0	2	1
ETAT-456		Lab based on Elective III or IV	0	2	1
ETAT-458		*Major project	0	12	8
TOTAL			13	20	26

*The student will submit a synopsis at the beginning of the semester for approval from the departmental committee in a specified format, thereafter he/she will have to present the progress of the work through seminars and progress reports. Seminar related to major project should be delivered one month after starting of Semester. The progress will be monitored through seminars and progress reports.

#Elective Paper will be floated if one-third of the total students opt for the same. It is advised that the decision about the elective subject is done before end of seventh semester. New Electives may be added as per requirement after getting it duly approved by cdc and dean respectively. **Syllabus may be revised after 2 years.

NOTE:

1. The total number of the credits (MAE) Programme = 214.
2. Each student shall be required to appear for examinations in all courses. However, for the award of the degree a student shall be required to earn minimum of 200 credits including Mandatory papers (M).

FOR LATERAL ENTRY STUDENTS:

1. The total number of the credits of the B.Tech. (MAE) Programme = 160.
2. Each student shall be required to appear for examinations in all courses Third Semester onwards. However, for the award of the degree a student shall be required to earn the minimum of 150 credits, including mandatory papers

Madan Bhandari Technological University

B.TECH AND M.TECH

1. ET stands for Engineering and Technology.
2. PE stands for Power Engineering.
3. ME stands for Mechanical Engineering.
4. MT stands for Mechatronics.
5. AT stands for Mechanical and Automation Engineering.
6. EE stands for Electrical and Electronics Engineering.
7. EL stands for Electrical Engineering.
8. IT stands for Information Technology
9. CS stands for Computer Science and Engineering
10. CE stands for Civil Engineering
11. EC stands for Electronics and Communications Engineering.
12. EN stands for Environmental Engineering
13. TE stands for Tool Engineering
14. MA stands for Mathematics
15. HS stands for Humanities and Social Sciences
16. SS stands for Social Services

Syllabus Detailing Sample:

Name of Subject

(EG---CE)

Year	I	Lecture	#
Semester	I/II	Tutorial	#
Course	Core/Elective	Practical	#

Course Description

This course provides an overview of

The students will be able to.....

Course Objectives

- To provide
- To provide
- To provide

Expected Learning Outcomes

Course Contents

Chapter	Chapter Title	Class Hours
1	<i>Name of Chapter 1</i> 1.1. 1.1.1. 1.2. 1.2.1..... 1.2.2..... 1.2.3..... 1.3. 1.3.1..... 1.3.2..... 1.3.3..... 1.3.4.....	#
2	<i>Name of Chapter 2</i> 2.1. 2.1.1. 2.2.	#
	Total Hours	##

List of Practical (if any)

- 1.
- 2.

Field Visit(if any)

Text books:(compulsory)

Tchobanoglous, G., Theisen, H., & Vigil, S. (1993).*Engineering principles and management Issues*.McGraw-Hill.

.....

Reference Texts:(compulsory)

1. Ramachandra, T. V. (2006). The Energy and Resources Institute (TERI).

Evaluation(compulsory)

Student evaluation will be done in marks out of 100 in total, which is sub-divided as:

Evaluation	Marks
Assessment Marks (50%)	50
Final Marks (50%)	50
Total Marks	100

The marks allocation for final examination will be accordingly as:

Chapter	Lecture Hours	Marks
1	#	@
2	#	@
3	#	@
4	#	@
5	#	@
6	#	@
7	#	@
Total	##	50

Sample Syllabus by Prof. R. C. Sapkota:

Applied Mechanics

EG 451 ME

Year	I	Lecture	3
Semester	II	Tutorial	1
Course	Core	Practical	0

Course Description

Applied mechanics is a branch of physical science that deals with the response of bodies to the application of forces. It bridges the gap between physical theory and its application to engineering problem solving.

This syllabus is designed to cover the basics of both statics and dynamics to be taught in one semester.

After completion of this course the students will be able to apply the concept and knowledge of mechanics for problem solving in engineering.

Course Objective

- To provide the students with basic concepts and knowledge of applied mechanics
- To make them able to use this basic knowledge of mechanics in different branches of engineering for problem solving

Course Contents

Chapter	Chapter Title	Class Hours
1	1. Introduction to Applied Mechanics 1.1 Definition and scope of applied mechanics 1.2 Concept of Rigid and Deformable Bodies, Fluids 1.3 Principles of Mechanics – Newton's Fundamental Laws	2
2	2. Basic Concept in Statics and Static Equilibrium 2.1 Concept of Particles and Rigid Body 2.2 Free Body Diagrams 2.3 Conditions of Equilibrium and its Essence in Structural Application 2.4 Equations of Equilibrium in Two Dimensions	4
3	3. Forces acting on particle and rigid body 3.1 Types of Forces and Free Body Diagrams, Examples 3.2 Point, Surface Traction and Body Forces, Translational and Rotational Forces 3.3 Resolution and Composition of Forces 3.4 Principle of Transmissibility and Equivalent Forces 3.5 Moments and Couples 3.6 Resolution of a Force into Forces and a Couple 3.7 Resultant of Force and Moment for a System of Forces	6
4	4. Center of Gravity, Centroid and Moment of Inertia 4.1. Centre of Gravity and Centroid, Methods of Calculation 4.2. Calculation of Second Moment of Area 4.3. Moment of Inertia and Radius of Gyration 4.4. Use of Parallel Axis Theorem, Related Problems	6
5	5. Friction 5.1 Types of friction, Advantages and disadvantages 5.2 Examples of uses of friction, Calculations involving Friction in Structures	2
6	6. Beams and Frames 5.3 Types of Beams and Frames, Types of Supports 5.4 Examples of Statically determinate and indeterminate structures 6.1 Calculation of Support Reactions: Active and Reactive Forces 6.2 Types of Loadings and Joints 6.3 Distributed Loads in Beams and Frames 6.4 Propped Cantilever and Portal Frame – introduction only 6.5 Calculation of Internal forces: Axial Force, Shear Force, and	9

	Bending Moment in Beams 6.6 Sign Convention 6.7 Shear Force and Bending Moment Diagrams	
7	7. <i>Analysis of Plane Trusses</i> 7.1 Types of Truss: Perfect, Deficient and Redundant Truss 7.2 Square truss with two diagonals 7.3 Uses of Truss in Engineering structures 7.4 Calculation of Member Forces of Truss: Method of Joints and Method of Sections	4
8	8. <i>Introduction to Dynamics: Newton's Laws</i> <i>Kinematics of Particles and Rigid Body</i> 8.1 Rectilinear Kinematics: 8.2 Position, Velocity and Acceleration of a Particles and Rigid Body 8.3 Determination of Motion of Particles and Rigid Body 8.4 Uniform Rectilinear Motion of Particles 8.5 Uniformly Accelerated Rectilinear Motion of Particles 8.6 Curvilinear Motion of particles	6
9	9. <i>Kinetics of Particles and Rigid Body</i> 9.1 Newton's Second Law: Force and Acceleration Method: For Particles and Rigid Bodies 9.2 Equations of Motion and Dynamic Equilibrium: For Particles and Rigid Body 9.3 Angular Momentum and Rate of Change 9.4 Equations of Motion: Rectilinear and Curvilinear Motion of Particles 9.5 Rectangular Coordinates: Tangential and Normal Components of Particles 9.6 Polar Coordinates: Radial and Traverse Components of particles	6
Total Contact Hours (lectures + tutorials) = 45 + 15= 60 hours		45

Tutorials

Tutorial classes shall be conducted by dividing the students of lecture class into two groups. Prepare necessary materials from each chapter that has to be taught using computers. There shall be at least one tutorial class per week per group, and students shall be assigned homework covering each unit accordingly.

Text Books:

1. "Mechanics of Engineers- Statics and Dynamics", F.P. Beer and E.R. Johnston, Jr. Latest Edition, McGraw-Hill.

2. "Engineering Mechanics-Statics and Dynamics", R.C. Hibbeler, Ashok Gupta. Latest Edition., New Delhi, Pearson.
3. "A Text Book of Applied Mechanics", Dr. RajanSuwal, 2nd Edition, Benchmark Publication, Kathmandu.

References:

1. "Engineering Mechanics- Statics and Dynamics", I.C. Jong and B.G. Rogers.
2. "Engineering Mechanics- Statics and Dynamics", D.K. Anand and P.F. Cunnif.

Evaluation

Student evaluation shall be done in 100 marks which is sub divisions as:

Evaluation	Marks
Assessment Marks (50%)	50
Final Marks (50%)	50
Total Marks	100

The marks allocation for final examination shall be accordingly as indicated in the table below:

Chapter	Lecture Hours	Marks
1	2	2
2	4	3
3	6	5
4	6	8
5	2	3
6	9	10
7	4	3
8	6	8
9	6	8
Total	45	50

Sample Questions:

Exam	Regular		
Level	BE	Full Marks	50
Program	BEL/BEX	Pass Marks	20
Year/part	I/II	Time	3 hrs

Subject: Applied mechanics (EG 451)

Q.No	Questions	Marks	Chapter
1. a)	Describe briefly the concepts of particle, rigid body and deformable body in the study of Mechanics	2	1
b)	What is a free body diagram? write the necessary and sufficient conditions of static equilibrium for a rigid body in two dimensions?	3	2
2. a)	<p>The resultant of a system of forces as shown in Fig. No.1 is 500 N and acts along X-axis towards the right. Calculate the magnitude of unknown force P and its inclination with X-axis.</p>	5	3
b)	Locate the coordinates of the centroid and calculate the Centre of gravity of the frustum of solid circular cone as given below with respect to its bottom.	8	4

3. a)	<p>A body of weight 600 N is placed on a rough horizontal surface and requires a horizontal force of 200 N to just move the block. Calculate the Resultant reaction and Coefficient of friction.</p>	4	5
b)	<p>Give examples of uses of truss in engineering structures. Name the different methods of finding out the forces in the members of a plane truss.</p>	3	7
4. a)	<p>Calculate the reaction forces at A and B for the beam loaded and supported as shown below. Draw shears force and bending</p>	9	6
b)	<p>The motion of a particle is defined by the relation $x=2t^3 -15t^2 + 24t +4$, where x is in meters and t in seconds. Determine when the velocity is zero and, the position and total distance travelled when the acceleration is zero.</p>	4	8
5. a)	<p>A bus starts from rest on a curved road of 250m radius and accelerates at the constant rate $a_t=0.6m/s^2$. Determine the distance and time that the bus will travel before the magnitude of its total acceleration is $0.75m/s^2$.</p>	4	8

b)	Write the equations of motion using rectangular coordinate system for a body in two dimension and three dimensions.	4	9
c)	Define angular momentum and describe time derivative of angular momentum with example.	4	

ON Going work

2. **Agricultural Technology** generate solutions to engineering problems within the fields of forestry, horticulture, agriculture, food processing and the environment.

Land-based engineers combine their technical ability with scientific knowledge to solve problems.

Typical responsibilities of the job include:

- designing and testing agricultural equipment including sprayers and ploughs
- designing and producing agricultural vehicles such as harvesters, tractors and loaders
- providing advice about soil conservation methods
- undertaking environmental impact assessments to determine the effect developments would have on the environment
- producing designs for and managing the construction of farm buildings
- working in emergency situations to restore water or electricity supplies following natural or human disasters
- designing, planning and overseeing the construction of irrigation and drainage systems
- writing and presenting reports
- carrying out relevant research
- giving technical support to customers and dealers
- providing consultancy services
- Suitable for rural construction

Qualifications and training required

There are routes into this profession for both graduates and school leavers. Graduates will need a degree in a relevant subject such as environmental engineering, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering or electronic engineering.

Key skills for land-based engineers

- Initiative
- Flexibility
- Ingenuity
- Good communication skills
- Technical skills
- Analytical skills
- Problem-solving skills

- IT skills
- Ability to work well within a team

Typical employers of land-based engineers

- Machinery dealerships
- Machinery manufacturers
- Government departments
- Universities
- Agricultural or environmental consultancies.

Master of Science in Agroforestry is a postgraduate Agriculture Science and Technology course. Agroforestry refers that it is an integrated approach of using the interactive benefits from combining trees and shrubs with crops and livestock. It combines agricultural and forestry technologies to create more diverse, productive, profitable, healthy and sustainable land-use systems. The duration of Master of Science in Agroforestry is two years and the syllabus is divided into major, minor, core and optional courses and it is also career orienting in nature.

M.Sc. Agroforestry Eligibility

They have passed the Four Year B.Sc. (Agri.)/three year B.Sc./Environmental Science examination of the University or an equivalent examination recognized by the University.

How is M.Sc. Agroforestry Course Beneficial?

After completing this diploma course candidates empower themselves of accessing and analyzing research outputs, policies, and trends in forestry, agroforestry and natural resources management and Agree on regional strategies for developing curricula and teaching materials. As it develops and adapts teaching methods and materials to national settings and improves access to appropriate teaching resources then it opens a lot of job scopes for diploma holders. They can go for higher degree research studies as well. The course also produces high calibre research scientists in the fields of tree biology, agroforestry science and natural resource management.

M.Sc. Agroforestry Job Types

Junior Research Fellow - Agroforestry

Manager - Forestry

Junior Research Fellow & Field Assistant

Relationship Manager - Retail Agriculture

Assistant Field Officer Trainee - Plantation

Research Scientist

Credit Manager - Loan against property

Associate Professor

Advance Course in M.Sc. Agroforestry: Ph.D. (Agroforestry)

B.Sc. (Forestry and Wood Technology) or Bachelor of Science in Forestry and Wood Technology is an undergraduate degree program of 5/4 years duration.

Forestry and Wood Technology is an area that focuses on managing forests in a sustainable manner.

Subjects studied under this degree include:

- Silviculture
- Agroforestry
- Forest Measurements
- Wood Science and Technology
- Forest Economics and Management
- Environmental Forestry

Basic Eligibility

A candidate must have passed the higher secondary school certificate (10+2) examination with science subject such as biology, maths, physics and chemistry from a recognized board.

Job Prospects

Candidates who opt for this career must have strong interest in science. Aspirants can also expand their skills and knowledge through pursuing more courses. After successful course completion, students can opt for:

- Bioinformatics
- Food industry
- Biotechnology
- Pharmaceutical industry
- Research institutes
- Water conservation

Option 1, In fourth and fifth as elective and core Even new students from admission As per the regulations prescribed by the University for the **M.Sc. Wood Science and Technology** Programme Candidates with Bachelor Degree in Chemistry/ Chemical Sciences/Physics/Botany/Plant Science/ Forestry/ Micro Biology/ Biotechnology/ Mathematics with at least

The Objective of the Course was to Strengthen the Process of Sustainable and Environment-Friendly Utilization of Timber Resource of the region through conduction of PG Programme relevant to the field of wood utilization and with a future aim of starting Doctoral Programme for carrying out research relevant to the concerned fields.

Option 2, Post Graduate Diploma in Forestry Management (PGDFM) is a postgraduate Forestry and Wildlife course. The degree course covers the areas of research for the students include silvi-culture, seed technology, agro-forestry, tree physiology, tree genetics, tree breeding, tree tissue culture, forest management, wood science, wildlife etc. Forestry is the art and science of tree resources, including plantations and natural stands. The main goal of

forestry is to create and implement systems that allow forests to continue a sustainable provision of environmental supplies and services.

How is Post Graduate Diploma in Forestry Management (PGDFM) Course Beneficial?

Organizations such as World Wildlife Fund and Food and Agricultural Organization etc are extending various opportunities for professionals in this field. Forest experts can find a lot of jobs in various sectors of timber and plywood manufacturing firms. They can also find jobs in laboratories or in offices in the related area. They can become forester who is responsible for protecting and regenerating forests, protecting wildlife habitats, checking for and fighting wild fires, landscape management and so on.

Eligibility

Students should have passed the degrees of B.Sc. (Forestry), B.Sc. (Ag), B.Sc. (Hort), B.Tech. (Hort), B.Tech. (Ag. Biotech.) can go for Master of Science in Forestry.

Post Graduate Diploma in Forestry Management (PGDFM) Syllabus

Syllabus of Forestry as prescribed by various Universities and Colleges.

Subjects of Study
Advanced Silvi-culture
Forest Biometric
Tree Breeding
Advanced Forest Ecology, Biodiversity and Conservation
Wood based Industries
Wildlife Management
Forest Protection
Agro forestry Practices

Post Graduate Diploma in Forestry Management (PGDFM) Course Suitability

Candidates should be used to of outdoors activities, spirit of adventure, good health, stamina and physical fitness. Other essential skills are patience, scientific temperament, organizing ability, public relations skills, practicality, courage and decision-making ability. They should have the capacity to work long hours, a genuine interest in the preservation of the natural environment and habitat, inclination for research and academic bent of mind. They should also be able to learn strategies like selecting and using training/instructional methods and procedures appropriate for the situation when learning or teaching new things.

Job Types

- Entomologist
- Dendrologist
- Foresters Silviculturist
- Zoo Curator
- National Sales Manager - Agri. Machinery
- Forest Range Officer

- Ethologist
- Sales/Business Development Officer
- Field Investigator

Model

Wildlife and Conservation Management Diploma typically **model offer**to complete and prepare students for entry-level careers as wildlife technicians. The coursework in wildlife and conservation management diploma programs teaches students how to conserve and manage the plants, animals, water and land found in wilderness areas, wildlife reservations and other outdoor recreation environments. Specific course topics may include:

- Wildlife management techniques
- Fish pond management
- Habitat manipulation
- Mammalogy
- Dendrology

Career Options

With a diploma in forestry or wildlife conservation, you may be able to find a job as a forest conservation worker. This job involves managing forest lands and maintaining facilities in the forest. You may need to remove sick trees and plants or spray insecticides to protect plant life from illnesses. Other responsibilities may include planting seeds or trees to encourage forest growth.

- **Model 2, Veterinary nurses** are vital to the running of a successful veterinary practice, and are responsible for working with veterinary surgeons to provide care and treatment to a variety of different animals such as dogs, cats and rabbits.
Being a vet nurse can be challenging; the role sometimes involves long and unsociable hours, however the sense of purpose that comes from nursing an ill animal back to health, and the long-lasting friendships fostered whilst working as part of a close knit team, make becoming a veterinary nurse a worthwhile ambition.
- **Model 3, Outdoor adventure guides** organize and conduct expeditions for sports enthusiasts, adventurers, tourists or resort guests. Outdoor Adventure Guides plan, guide and coach groups and individuals in outdoor adventure activities. They work for adventure tourism companies, resorts, parks, lodges or campgrounds, or they operate their own small businesses. They might take clients white water rafting, fishing, hunting, or mountain climbing, depending on the season and on their skills. Often the work is seasonal, and, depending on the type of guiding, the hours can be irregular. They may specialise in one particular activity or offer a variety of activities for clients. They must be able to instruct clients in outdoor adventure activities, ensuring the safety of the entire group.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

- Outdoor adventure guides don't typically need any formal post-secondary education to work as an outdoor adventure guide. Pursuing education in a related field however, can provide you with skills, knowledge and competencies that can be very helpful in this career.
if you plan on running your own outdoor adventure business, having coursework in marketing, management, and business administration can be extremely helpful.

SKILL REQUIREMENTS

- In order to execute your job duties with competence, you'll need to be armed with certain skills, including:
 - Ability to deal with physical demands of the position
 - Previous experience in the relevant sport or activity is required
 - Ability to work in teams
 - Excellent communication skills
 - Excellent instructional skills is required
 - Good organizational skills
 - Leadership skills
 - Working knowledge of terrain, environment and local area
 - Good customer relations skills
 - Working knowledge of relevant legislation
 - Knowledge and mechanical skills necessary to maintain your equipment
 - If self-employed, need skills in small business (such as marketing, accounting, management, etc.)

JOB MARKET

- Data on Job Outlook are updated on a yearly basis and are compiled from national statistics which may not reflect either regional variations or more recent changes in employment conditions.
- Over the five years to November 2019, the number of job openings for Outdoor Adventure Guides is expected to be low (equal to or less than 5,000). Job openings count both employment growth and turnover (defined as workers leaving their occupation for other employment or leaving the workforce). Further information about job openings and projected employment growth is available on the Help page.
- Employment for this occupation rose strongly (in percentage terms) in the past five years and rose very strongly in the long-term (ten years). Looking forward, employment for Outdoor Adventure Guides to November 2020 is expected to grow moderately.
- This is a very small occupation (2600 in November 2015) suggesting that opportunities may be quite limited in some regions.

- Outdoor Adventure Guides have a below average proportion of full-time jobs (65.8 per cent). For Outdoor Adventure Guides working full-time, average weekly hours are 36.1 (compared to 40.2 for all occupations). Unemployment for Outdoor Adventure Guides is below average.

Institutes Offering B.Sc. - Forestry and Wood Technology

- Beehive College of Management & Technology - Bachelor of Science in Forestry
- BFIT Group of Institutions - Bachelor of Science in Forestry
- Chandra Shekhar Azad University of Agriculture and Technology - Bachelor Of Science in Forestry
- Chhattisgarh University - Bachelor of Science in Forest Resources
- Dr. BalasahebSawantKonkanKrishiVidyapeeth - Bachelor of Science in Forestry
- MaharanaPratap University of Agriculture and Technology - Bachelor of Science in Forestry
- Rai Technology University - Bachelor of Science in Forestry
- SaiNath University - Bachelor of Science in Forestry
- Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology of Kashmir, Faculty of Agriculture - Bachelor of Science in Forestry
- Sir Syed College - Bachelor of Science in Forestry and Wood Technology
- University of Agricultural Sciences - Bachelor of Science in Forestry
- Uttaranchal Institute of Technology - Bachelor of Science in Forestry

B. Tech Construction Technology is an undergraduate Construction Technology course. The program provides courses in construction science covering the heavy civil, commercial, and residential fields. Students will learn about construction materials and green building methods through the use of readings, 3-D models, hands-on laboratory exercises, and site visits. Construction Management courses in estimating; scheduling, BIM, job site management, safety, and soil testing are also provided. Students will build a strong background in mathematics, computer technology, business, and other general education subjects.

How is Bachelor of Construction Technology Course Beneficial?

The Course is beneficial to prepare graduates for future roles in managing people, equipment, materials, technological processes and funds in the construction, building and maintenance of buildings and assets in the civil infrastructure. They can pursue careers as construction managers, project engineers/managers, civil engineers and asset management engineers in a range of industries including consulting engineering, construction, research organizations, private sector, local and other government authorities. They can also go for further research studies after completing this course. Degree prepares students for roles in management functions such as project management, estimating, and scheduling. Students learn the basic engineering principles and technical skills necessary to help engineers and other professionals supervise the construction of buildings and other structures.

Eligibility

- XII with Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics or equivalent with minimum 55% marks.

Syllabus

Subjects of Study
Engineering Mathematics
Materials of Construction
Strength of Materials
Surveying
Management Theory – Principles and Practices
Applied Engineering Geology
Survey Practice
Construction Materials Testing Lab
Building Construction
Structural Analysis
Concrete Technology
Financial and Cost Accounting
Construction Planning and Control
Design of Structures
Geo-technical Engineering
Construction Economics and Finance
Transportation Engineering
Building Drawing
CAD Lab
Construction Technology Laboratory
Construction Quality Management
Contracts and Specifications
Irrigation Engineering and Hydraulic Structures
Construction Methods & Equipments
Geo-technology Lab
Construction Study Project
Constitutional Law and Professional Ethics
Design of Prestressed Concrete Structures
Quantitative Surveying & Estimation

Building Services
Building Services Lab
Building Planning, Types & Standards
Project Work
Seminar
Electives
Ground Improvement Techniques
Design of Masonry Structures
Advanced Surveying
Fundamentals of Architecture
Pre-fabrication Construction Techniques
Advanced Design of R.C. Structures
Urban and Regional Planning
Landscape Design and Planning
Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing
Alternative Building Materials and Technologies
Rural water supply and Sanitation
Computer Applications in Construction Engineering and Planning
Applied Geo-Technical Engineering
Building Climatology
Distress Diagnostics, Repair and Rehabilitation of Structures
Bridge Engineering
Foundation Engineering
Special Concretes
Geographic Information System (GIS)
Project Safety Management

Course Suitability

They should have problem solving skills used on a daily basis in the construction industry; from dealing with the unexpected, such as burst water pipes, to minimising delays. They also possess time management skills such as in complex construction projects it requires effective organisation and time management if they are to be delivered to budget and on time. Candidates are also expected to possess a variety of different skill sets in order to be successful, including knowledge of the construction industry, technical skills and computer proficiency.

Job Types

- Framing and Finish Carpenter

- Siding Installer
- Maintenance Welder
- Deck Builder
- Roofer
- Dry-waller
- Remodeler
- Electrician

TITLE OF THE PROGRAMME

BACHELOR OF VOCATION IN CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY

Preamble

Construction activity is an integral part of nation's infrastructure and industrial development. Construction industry is vital in socio-economic development and also generates substantial employment and provides a growth impetus to other sectors through backward and forward linkages. Construction Technology deals with design, construction and maintenance of hospitals, schools, townships, offices, houses and other buildings; urban infrastructure (including water supply, sewerage, drainage); highways, roads, ports, railways, airports; power systems; irrigation and agriculture systems; telecommunications; dams, bridges, tunnels and other structures. Requirement of skilled personnel/ technicians in construction engineering works is growing day to day. Construction industries, public & private entrepreneurs, government organizations, builders, Real Estate owners are in need of technicians in this area. Hence this course has several advantages that will enable student to get engaged in any civil engineering work area.

Objectives of course

The B. Voc in Construction Technology aims at providing the expertise needed to effectively lead a construction project and work with industry. It aims at providing over all technical proficiency, the industrial working exposure, and the entrepreneurial skills for success in this ever-evolving industry.

The curriculum teaches you how to integrate multiple professional requirements for bringing construction projects to successful completion, including building construction, planning and drafting, estimating, cost control, new technologies, methods of surveying & advanced surveying, concrete technology, geo-technology, structural design, CAD, water management & sanitation, transportation engineering, project planning, scheduling & negotiation, and labour management etc. The coursework aims at managing various types of contractual relationships governing the owner, the contractor, subcontractors, consultants, and architects, as well as the essential skills of bidding, negotiating, handling disputes and claims. To train the students to gear up to employment opportunities in construction industry in Private & Public sectors, state and central public works departments and other Government undertakings, Self-employment ventures/ Civil Engineering Contractor etc.

Program Structure

The course titled as B. Voc. (Construction Technology) is proposed with Bridge course and modular structure that gives exit option after every year with employable skill at the end of each module. The three modules are as under:

All students should undergo bridge course program of 180 hrs duration in each semester for first two semesters along with level-5 regular course (i.e. first year of B.Voc). The credits earned are of qualifying nature and

should be completed within four semesters (2 years) for obtaining Diploma/Advanced Diploma/ B.Voc Degree, as a pre-requisite. A certificate to this effect shall be issued by the Principal/Director of affiliated Institutes to be submitted to COE. NSQF LEVEL-IV certification may be done through the respective agencies involved.

Program Outcomes

1. Diploma in Construction Technology

Outcome: Student shall have acquired adequate skills to assist and work as surveyor, drafts man, supervisor and site engineer. After successful completion of this module and some additional practice the student should have attained

- Skill in preparing, reading and interpreting drawing pertaining to Civil engineering and allied works
- Understanding the use of various types of construction materials, their characteristics and suitability in construction sector
- Ability to perform surveying works for various construction works & exposure to various digital equipment
- Competencies in estimating and costing and contracting of civil works including measurement and billing
- Knowledge of appropriate attitude and values and awareness regarding ecology and environment engineering
- Skill in using computers in the field of civil engineering

2. Advanced Diploma in Construction Technology

Outcome: Student shall have acquired adequate skills to work as surveyor, drafts man, supervisor and site engineer. Student can work as an assistant to mix designer, project manager and design engineer. After successful completion of this module and some additional practice the student should have attained

- Understanding of concepts, principles and practices in making concrete and concreting operations for different types of civil works
- Analytical ability and understanding of behaviour of various types of soils and their uses for civil works
- Analytical ability and understanding of behaviour of fluid mechanics and its applications
- Analysis and design of simple structural elements in concrete and steel and skill of preparing and reading detailed structural drawings
- Awareness regarding facilities and support system to promote entrepreneurship development
- Ability to use the knowledge of building services in preparing computer based drawings as per requirements
- Design of pavements in transportation engineering
- Ability to perform surveying works for various construction works using digital equipment

3. Bachelor of Vocation in Construction Technology

Outcome: Student shall have acquired adequate skills to work as surveyor, drafts man, supervisor, site engineer, mix designer, Technical Report writer, project manager and design engineer. Further it opens the gates to further vertical mobility in career. After

successful completion of this module and some additional practice the student should be able to take up his own self-employment ventures/contracts/projects

- Ability to supervise various civil works such as buildings, industrial structures, bridges, tunnels roads, irrigation structures, water works etc.
- Application of knowledge of planning, scheduling, controlling and skill of advanced surveying in supervising various construction projects
- Skill in managing construction materials, equipment, manpower and cash flow
- Competencies in maintenance, repairs and upkeep of building
- Knowledge of principles of water supply and sanitary engineering and methods of treating water and sewage
- Rigorous training in enhancing communication skills, technical English and interpersonal relations and skills in communication
- Awareness regarding hazards, safety measures at construction site
- Awareness about Contract laws & regulation, Disaster Management, waste management
- Exposure to various computation skills such as MATLAB and Civil engineering design and drafting software
- Ability in preparing computer based structural drawings

PREAMBLE

It has been a long felt necessity to align higher education with the emerging needs of the economy so as to ensure that the graduates of higher education system have adequate knowledge and skills for employment and entrepreneurship. The higher education system has to incorporate the requirements of various industries in its curriculum, in an innovative and flexible manner while developing a holistic and well-groomed graduate. The University Grants Commission (UGC) has launched a scheme on skills development based higher education as part of college/university education, leading to Bachelor of Vocation (B.Voc.) Degree with multiple exits such as Diploma/Advanced Diploma under the NSQF (National Skills Qualifications Framework)

PROGRAMS

Vocational, or skills-based, education is becoming more and more significant in today's perspective as industry expecting new employees to have all the practical skills they need to start work. Keeping in view the demands of the industry and to provide flexible options for students as desired by UGC the Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University have launched Bachelor of Vocation courses in 10 sectors namely during academic year 2015-16.

1. Applied Art
2. Interior Design
3. Automobile
4. Construction Technology
5. Consumer Electronics
6. Mobile Communication

7. Printing & Publishing
8. Power Distribution and Management
9. Refrigeration & Air Conditioning
10. Software Development

These programmes aim to build individual capacities and train persons with adequate employability skills. The programme structure attempts to blend appropriate technical knowledge and skills, personal and professional skills and substantive 'hands-on' and field / site experience required in the trade.

Eligibility for admission into B.Voc:

- Courses 1&2: candidates having obtained minimum 50% in 10+2 in any stream
- Courses 3 to 10: candidates having obtained minimum 50% in 10+2 in Science Stream (Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics)
- 10+2 years ITI (of the analogous stream)
- The candidates should not be less than 16 years and more than 45 years

The program structure:

Levels of Awards:

The certification levels will lead to Diploma/Advanced Diploma/B. Voc. Degree in one or more vocational areas and will be offered under the aegis of the University.

Duration: 6 Semesters (3 years). This three year full time programme is divided into six semesters, each of 15 weeks including assessment. In addition all students are expected to undergo industrial training / project work for 4-8 weeks every semester that may continue partly during summer / winter breaks. All students should undergo bridge course program of 180 hrs duration in each semester for first two semesters along with level 5 regular course. The credits earned are of qualifying nature and should be completed within four semesters (2 years) for obtaining Diploma/Advanced Diploma/ B.Voc Degree, as a pre-requisite. A certificate to this affect shall be issued by the Principal/Director of affiliated Institutes to be submitted to COE. NSQF LEVEL-IV certification may be done through the respective agencies involved.

Bachelor of Vocation

Construction Technology

Bridge Course for (10+2 pcm)/10+ITI Students

(First Semester Examination)

no. of hours: 12 x 15 =180

Bachelor of Vocation

Construction Technology

Bridge Course for (10+2 pcm)/10+ITI Students

(Second Semester Examination)

No. of hours: 12 x 15 =180

Note: The students are advised to mandatorily complete the bridge course alongwith LEVEL-V regular course. The credits earned are of qualifying nature and should be completed within four semesters (2 years) for obtaining Diploma/Advanced Diploma/ B.Voc Degree, as a pre-requisite. A certificate to this affect shall be issued by the Principal/Director of affiliated Institutes to be submitted to COE. NSQF LEVEL-IV certification may be done through the respective agencies involved.

BRIDGE WORKSHOP-I

Paper Code: ETVCT-401 (L T/P C)

Paper: Bridge Workshop-I 044

Objectives and Pre-requisites: To have a balanced overall development of student; To integrate theory with practice; To provide hand on experience about use of different tools and basic manufacturing practices; To develop general manual and machining skills in the students.

Learning outcomes: Students are able to respect and visualize dignity of labour, precision, safety at work place, team working and development of right attitude.

DETAILED CONTENTS (PRACTICAL EXERCISES)

Note: The students are supposed to come in proper workshop dress prescribed by the institute. Wearing shoes in the workshop(s) is compulsory. Importance of safety and cleanliness, safety measures and upkeep of tools, equipment and environment in each of the following shops should be explained and practiced. The students should prepare sketches of various tools/jobs in their practical Notebook.

MASONRY SHOP

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used tools.
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in Plumbing shop.
3. Preparation of mortar and cement concrete
4. Importance of form work and material used in form work
5. Slab, lintel & sunshade, column & footing and beam reinforcement
6. Differentiate and demonstrate steel reinforcement bars of different diameters (plain bar, ribbed, tor steel etc.)

CARPENTRY SHOP

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used hand tools.
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in carpentry shop.
3. Introduction to various types of wood such as Deodar, Kail, Partal, Teak, Mango, Sheesham, etc. (Demonstration and their identification).
4. Marking, sawing, planning and chiseling & their practice (size should be mentioned)
5. Introduction to various types of wooden joints, their relative advantages and uses.

PAINTING SHOP

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used tools.
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in painting shop.
3. Demonstration of various types of paints used
4. Methods of painting wooden items
5. Preparation of wooden surface before painting including primer coating

FITTING SHOP

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used tools.
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in fitting shop.
3. Introduction to common materials used in fitting shop
4. Identification of materials. Such as Steel, Brass, Copper, Aluminium etc.
5. Identification of various sections of steel such as Flat, Angle, Tee, Channel, Bar Girder, Square, Z-Section, etc.
6. Demonstration of various types of work benches, holding devices.

WELDING SHOP

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used tools.
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in welding shop.
3. Introduction to welding and its importance in engineering practice
4. Introduction to welding equipment and safety precautions during hazards of welding and its remedies.
5. Practice in setting current and voltage for striking proper arc. Earthing of welding machine.

References Books:

- [R1] Workshop Technology I,II,III, by S K Hajra, Choudhary and A K Chaoudhary; Media Promoters and Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Bombay
- [R2] Workshop Technology by Manchanda Vol. I,II,III; India Publishing House, Jalandhar.
- [R3] Manual on Workshop Practice by K Venkata Reddy, KL Narayana et al; MacMillan India Ltd. New Delhi
- [R4] Basic Workshop Practice Manual by T Jeyapooan; Vikas Publishing House (P) Ltd., New Delhi
- [R5] Workshop Technology by B.S. Raghuwansh;,DhanpatRai and Co., New Delh
- [R6] Workshop Technology by HS Bawa; Tata McGraw Hill Publishers, New Delhi

I.T. WORKSHOP-I

(BASICS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY- I)

Paper Code: ETVCT-403 L T/P C

Paper: Basics of Information Technology-I 0 4 4

Objectives & Prerequisites:

To study and understand the fundamentals of computer system. To learn details of hardware and software components. Proper exposure to various aspects of information technology such as understanding the concept of information technology and its scope; operating a computer; use of various tools of MS Office/Open Office and internet form the broad competency profile of students. To have rigorous practice of MS word, Excel and power point tools. To use MS office tools to prepare desired assignments. Basic mathematical knowledge and willingness to excel are the basic prerequisites.

Learning outcomes:

This exposure will enable the students to enter their professions with confidence, live in a harmonious way and contribute to the productivity. Being a bridge course it helps in understanding of software and CAD in the later stages of the course. Useful in preparing project reports in both academic and professional fronts.

DETAILED CONTENTS (PRACTICAL EXERCISES)

1. To study concept and scope, applications of IT, ethics and future with information technology
2. A report on impact of computer and IT in society
3. A report on Generations of computer, block diagram of a computer, CPU, memory, data – numeric data, alpha numeric data, processing of data.
4. To study about Computer hardware and software; primary and secondary memory: Input devices; output devices
5. To study Introduction to Operating Systems such as MS-DOS and Windows, difference between DOS and Windows.
6. To understand Basics of Networking – LAN, MAN, WAN
7. To Identify and list functions of various components and peripherals of given computer.
8. Installation of operating system viz. * Windows XP, *Windows 2007 etc.
9. Installing a computer system by giving connection and loading the system software and application software and various sources to install software
10. Exercises on entering text and data (Typing Practice)
11. To practice Features of Windows as an operating system:
 - a) Start , shutdown and restore
 - b) Creating and operating on the icons
 - c) Opening, closing and resizing the windows
 - d) Using elementary job commands like – creating, saving, modifying, renaming, finding and deleting a file , creating and operating on a folder
 - e) Introduction to all properties such as changing settings like, date, time, calculator, colour (back ground and fore ground)
 - f) Using short cuts
12. Word Processing (MS Office/Open Office)- To prepare a report using various features of MS word

- a) File Management:
 - b) Opening, creating and saving a document, locating files, copying contents in some different file(s)
 - c) Editing a document:
 - d) Entering text, cut, copy, paste using toolbars
 - e) Use of spell check
 - f) PDF file and its conversion in different file formats (MS Word/Excel etc.)
 - g) Scanning, editing and printing of a document
 - h) Formatting a document:
 - i) Using different fonts, changing font size and colour, changing the appearance through bold/ italic/ underlined, highlighting a text, changing case, using subscript and superscript, using different underline methods
 - j) Aligning of text in a document, justification of document ,Inserting bullets and numbering
 - k) Formatting paragraph, inserting page breaks and column breaks, line spacing
 - l) Use of headers, footers, inserting footnote, end note, use of comments
 - m) Inserting date, time, special symbols, importing graphic images, drawing tools

 - n) Tables and Borders:
 - o) Creating a table, formatting cells, use of different border styles, shading in tables, merging of cells, partition of cells, inserting and deleting a row in a table
 - p) How to change docx file to doc file
 - q) Print preview, zoom, page set up, printing options
 - r) Using Find, Replace options
13. Spread Sheet Processing (MS Office/Open Office) - To prepare a report using various features of MS excel
- a) Starting Excel
 - b) open worksheet, enter, edit data, formulae to calculate values, format data, create chart, printing chart, save worksheet, switching between different spread sheets
 - c) Menu commands: Create, format charts, organize, manage data, solving problem by analyzing data, creating graphs
 - d) Work books: Managing workbooks (create, open, close, save, rename), working in work books
 - e) Editing a worksheet: copying, moving cells, pasting, inserting, deleting cells, rows, columns, find and replace text, numbers of cells, formatting worksheet
 - f) Creating a chart: Working with chart types, changing data in chart, formatting a chart, use chart to analyze data
 - g) Using a list to organize data, sorting and filtering data in list
 - h) Formulas: Addition, subtraction, division, multiplication, percentage and auto sum
 - i) Introduction to PowerPoint

14. Power Point Presentation (MS Office/Open Office)- To prepare a power point presentation
- a) Introduction to PowerPoint
 - b) How to start PowerPoint
 - c) Working environment: concept of toolbars, slide layout, templates etc.
 - d) Opening a new/existing presentation
 - e) Different views for viewing slides in a presentation: normal, slide sorter etc.
 - f) Addition, deletion and saving of slides
 - g) Insertion of multimedia elements
 - h) Adding text boxes, importing pictures, tables and charts etc.
 - i) Formatting slides: Text formatting, changing slide layout, changing slide colour scheme
 - j) Changing background, Applying design template
 - k) How to view the slide show?
 - l) Viewing the presentation using slide navigator, Slide transition
 - m) Animation effects etc.

Note:

Explanation of Introductory part and theory should be dovetailed with practical work. Following topics may be explained in the laboratory along with the practical exercises. There will not be any theory examination.

References Books:

- [R1] Fundamentals of Computer by E. Balagurusamy, Tata McGraw Hill Education Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi
- [R2] Fundamentals of Computer by V Rajaraman; Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi
- [R3] Computer Fundamentals by PK Sinha; BPB Publication, New Delhi
- [R4] MS Office by BPB Publications, New Delhi

ENGINEERING DRAWING-I

Paper Code: ETVCT-405 L T/P C

Paper: Engineering Drawing-I 0 4 4

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

Maximum Marks: 75

-
1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
 2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Prerequisites & Objectives: Drawing is said to be the language of engineers and technicians. Reading and interpreting engineering drawing is their day-to-day

responsibility. The course is aimed at developing basic graphic skills so as to enable them to use these skills in preparation of engineering drawings, their reading and interpretation.

Learning outcomes: Being bridge course it helps understanding the concepts of Civil engineering drawing and drafting in later stages. Helps in understanding CAD in later stages. Improved abilities of draftsman ship.

DETAILED CONTENTS

1. Study of Drawing Office Practice tools- Drawing instruments, Sizes and layout of standard drawing sheets, Sizes of drawing boards, drafting table/board.
2. To draw and practice Different types of Lines and Free Hand Sketching (minimum 1 sheet).
3. Different types of lines in engineering drawing as per BIS specifications.
4. Practice in free hand sketching of vertical, horizontal and inclined lines, geometrical figures such as triangles, rectangles, small and large circles, parabolas, curves and ellipses.
5. Lettering Techniques and Practice- Instrumental single stroke (capital and inclined) lettering of 35 mm height in the ratios of 7:4.
6. Lettering Techniques and Practice- Instrumental double stroke lettering of 35 mm height in the ratio of 7:4, vertical.
7. Free hand lettering (alphabet and numerals) lower case and upper case, single stroke vertical and inclined at 75 degree in different standard series of 2.5, 3, 5, 7, 10, and 15 mm heights in the ratio of 7:4.
8. Dimensioning- Necessity of dimensioning, terms and notations – methods and principles, dimensioning small components (practice & theoretical instructions).
9. Dimensioning of overall sizes, circles, thread holes, chamfered surfaces, angles, tapered surface holes equally spaced on PCD, counter sunk hole counter bored holes, cylindrical parts, narrow space and gaps, radii, curves and arches – chain and parallel dimensioning.
10. Scales – their need and importance, Definition of representative fraction (RF); Find RF of a given scale.
11. Study Types of scales.
12. Construction of plain and diagonal scales.
13. Principle of orthographic projection & Projection of points situated in different quadrants.
14. Projection of lines, Lines inclined to one plane and parallel to the other and vice versa.
15. Projection of Planes: Planes perpendicular and parallel to either of the planes; planes perpendicular to one plane and parallel to the other or vice versa.

References Books:

- [R1] ND Bhatt, V.M. Panchal, Engineering Drawing-Planes & Solid Geometry”, Charotar publishing house Principles of Building Drawing by MG Shah and CM Kale, MacMillan, Delhi
- [R2] Zaidi, SKA and Siddiqui, Suhail; “Drawing and Design of Residential and Commercial Buildings”, Standard Publishers and Distributors, Delhi.
- [R3] Surjit Singh, “Engineering Drawing: A Text Book of Engineering Drawing, DhanpatRai& Co.

BRIDGE WORKSHOP-II

Paper Code: ETVCT-402 L T/P C

Paper: Bridge Workshop-II 0 4 4

Objectives and Pre-requisites:To have a balanced overall development of student; To integrate theory with practice; To provide hand on experience about use of different tools and basic manufacturing practices; To develop general manual and machining skills in the students.

Learning outcomes: Students are able to respect and visualize dignity of labour, precision, safety at work place, team working and development of right attitude.

DETAILED CONTENTS (PRACTICAL EXERCISES)

Note: The students are supposed to come in proper workshop dress prescribed by the institute. Wearing shoes in the workshop(s) is compulsory. Importance of safety and cleanliness, safety measures and upkeep of tools, equipment and environment in each of the following shops should be explained and practiced. The students should prepare sketches of various tools/jobs in their practical Notebook.

PLUMBING & SANITATION

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used tools. Necessity of plumbing, Technical terms used
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in Plumbing shop.
3. GI pipe marking, threading, cutting and jointing
4. PVC pipe marking, cutting, threading and jointing
5. Use of PPR and their jointing
6. Building services, types of valves and uses
7. Water meter connection, water closets, flush tanks
8. Field visit

SHEET METAL SHOP

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used tools.
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in sheet metal shop.
3. Demonstration of various machines and equipment used in sheet metal shop.

4. Demonstration of various raw materials used in sheet metal.

SMITHY SHOP

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used tools.
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in smithy shop.
3. Forging operations in smithy shop. Safety measures to be observed in the smithy shop.
4. Demonstration and description of bending operation, upsetting operation.
5. Description and specification of anvils, swage blocks, hammers etc.
6. Demonstration and description of tongs, fullers, swages etc.

ELECTRICAL SHOP

1. Demonstration, function and use of commonly used tools.
2. Care, maintenance of tools and safety measures to be observed in Electrical shop.
3. Familiarization with various electrical tools and safety measures
4. Study of various types of wirings: conduit/concealed/batten etc
5. Study of distribution boards
6. Various types of faults in house wiring

References Books:

- [R1] Workshop Technology I, II,III, by S K Hajra, Choudhary and A K Chaoudhary; Media Promoters and Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Bombay
- [R2] Workshop Technology by Manchanda Vol.I, II, III; India Publishing House, Jalandhar.
- [R3] Manual on Workshop Practice by K Venkata Reddy, KL Narayana et al; MacMillan India Ltd. New Delhi
- [R4] Basic Workshop Practice Manual by T Jeyapoovan; Vikas Publishing House (P) Ltd., New Delhi
- [R5] Workshop Technology by B.S. Raghuwansh;,DhanpatRai and Co., New Delh
- [R6] Workshop Technology by HS Bawa; Tata McGraw Hill Publishers, New Delhi

I.T. WORKSHOP-II

(BASICS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY-II)

Paper Code: ETVCT-404 L T/P C

Paper: Basics of Information Technology-II 0 4 4

Objectives & Pre-requisites:

To understand the utility of antivirus, various types, its installation, usage to remove virus from corrupted files. To understand the power of internet.To open email account operating with email.To learn the fundamentals of basics of computer programming.To study and understand various features of C/C++. To be in a position to write programs involve general logic and technical in nature. Basic mathematical knowledge, basics of information technology and willingness to excel in computer programming are the basic prerequisites.

Learning outcomes:

This exposure will enable the students to enter their professions with confidence, live in a harmonious way and contribute to the productivity. Being a bridge course it helps in understanding of software and CAD in the later stages of the course. Ability to develop and write programs in C/C++ for various problems while developing and preparing project reports in both academic and professional fronts.

DETAILED CONTENTS (PRACTICAL EXERCISES)

1. Antivirus- installation & scanning of corrupted files
 - a) What is virus and its types
 - b) Problems due to virus
 - c) Installation and updation of antivirus (anyone out of Kaspersky, McAfee, Norton, Quickhealetc).
 - d) How to scan and remove the virus
2. Practice of Internet surfing and its Applications
 - a) Log-in to internet, introduction to search engine
 - b) Browsing and down loading of information from internet
 - c) Creating e-Mail Account, Log in to e-mail account and Log out from e-mail account
 - d) Managing e-Mail- Creating, Sending, receiving, forwarding, deleting, attaching a file
3. Introduction to programming- “C/C++”
 - a) Development of C, starting with C- alphabets, digits, special symbols
 - b) Constants, variables and special symbols
 - c) Instructions
4. Study of C- pre-processor features
5. Study of structures- case control structures, loops control structures and decision control structures
6. Study of input output functions, types of functions
7. Study of file concept- opening, reading, closing, writing etc
8. Study and use of concept of pointers
9. Study the concept of arrays

Note:

Explanation of Introductory part and theory should be dovetailed with practical work. Emphasis should be more on programming techniques rather than language itself. Students are encouraged to develop algorithms of programs and practicing in the laboratory along with the practical exercises. There will not be any theory examination.

References Books:

- [R1] Internet for Every One by Alexis Leon and Mathews Leon; Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., Jungpura, New Delhi

- [R2] Fundamentals of Computer by EBalagurusamy, Tata McGraw Hill Education Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi
- [R3] Programming with C by Byron Gottfried, Schaum's outline series, McGraw Hill Education series.
- [R4] Programming in ANSI C by E. Balaguswamy, McGraw Hill Education series

ENGINEERING DRAWING-II

Paper Code: ETVCT-406 L T/P C

Paper: Engineering Drawing-II 0 4 4

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Prerequisites & Objectives: Drawing is said to be the language of engineers and technicians. Reading and interpreting engineering drawing is their day-to-day responsibility. The course is aimed at developing basic graphic skills so as to enable them to use these skills in preparation of engineering drawings, their reading and interpretation.

Learning outcomes: Being bridge course it helps understanding the concepts of Civil engineering drawing and drafting in later stages. Exposure CAD software enhances the confidence of the student and his abilities of draftsman ship.

DETAILED CONTENTS

1. Need for sectional views
 - a. cutting planes methods of representing sections
 - b. conventional sections of various material
 - c. classification of sections
 - d. conventions in sectioning
2. Drawing of full section, half section, partial or broken out section, offset sections, revolved sections & removed sections. Exercises on sectional views of different objects.
3. Drawing of different conventions for materials in sections. Conventional breaks for shafts, pipes: Rectangular /square/circular, angle, channel and Rolled sections.
4. Fundamentals of isometric projections and draw Isometric views from given orthographic views
5. Symbols, Conventions and simple drawing of Sanitary fitting symbols
6. Draw the Electrical fittings Symbols for domestic interior installations
7. Building plan drawing with Electrical and Civil Engineering symbols.

8. Introduction to CAD & Installation of CAD software
9. AutoCAD- An over view
10. Definition and practice of various commands used in AUTOCAD
11. Using CAD software draw different Geometric Constructions
 - a. Divide a given line into desired number of equal parts internally
 - b. Draw tangent lines and arcs
 - c. Construct a hexagon from the given data
 - d. Construct ellipse, parabola, hyperbola, cycloid, and helix.
12. Using AUTOCAD software draw conventional signs as per I. S. standards and , different symbols used in civil engineering drawing & dimensioning and lettering

INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY

Teachers are expected to develop skills in preparation of proper drawings with emphasis onto prepare drawings on AutoCAD as per IS code of practice. Attention must be paid towards line work, specifications writing, dimensioning, proportioning and accuracy. At different intervals of time, practice of reading and interpreting actual field drawing should also be practiced so as to develop necessary competencies in the students.

References Book(s):

- [R1] ND Bhatt, V.M. Panchal, “Engineering Drawing–Planes & Solid Geometry”, Charotar Publishing House.
- [R2] MG Shah and CM Kale, “Principles of Building Drawing”, MacMillan, Delhi
- [R3] Zaidi, SKA and Siddiqui, Suhail; “Drawing and Design of Residential and Commercial Buildings”, Standard Publishers and Distributors, Delhi.
- [R4] Surjit Singh, “Engineering Drawing: A Text Book of Engineering Drawing”, DhanpatRai& Co.
- [R5] RS Malik, “Civil Engineering Drawing”, Asia Publishing House
- [R6] National Building Code

**SCHEME OF EXAMINATION And SYLLABI for BACHELOR OF
VOCATION in
CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY
Offered by
University School of Engineering and Technology**

1st SEMESTER to 6th SEMESTER

Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University
Dwarka, Delhi – 110078 [INDIA]
www.ipu.ac.in

**BACHELOR OF VOCATION
(CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY)
FIRST SEMESTER EXAMINATION
(LEVEL-V)**

***Industrial Training-I:** The students are advised to undergo two weeks training in house/industry/ Skill Knowledge Provider (SKP)/ Sector Skill Council (SSC) during winter Vacation and should submit training report for evaluation during the second semester.

****General Elective –II (Select any One):** NCC, NSS, YOGA, Sports, Community Services, ECO Club

Note: The student can opt to take General Elective-II during the first to fifth semesters and can earn credits and /or certificate as per the requirements of the course opted for during the fifth semester. The camps or classes for the said programme can be held either during weekend/holidays or winter/summer vacations. If in case, the classes are held during Saturday /Sunday then faculty should be given off in lieu of Saturday/Sunday. Those students who complete General Electives-II shall be given certificate if they opt out of the programme taking Diploma/Advanced Diploma.

Note: It is very important to decide the General Elective(s), Core Elective(s) and Open Elective(s) to be offered in the next semester well before the completion of current semester. General/Core/Open Elective Paper(s) will be floated if about 50% (Not Less than 1/3rd) of the total students opt for the same in each case.

**BACHELOR OF VOCATION
(CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY)
SECOND SEMESTER EXAMINATION
(LEVEL-V)**

Note for Project: The student will submit a synopsis at the beginning of the semester for approval from the departmental committee in a specified format, thereafter he/she will have to present the progress of the work through seminars and progress reports.

Industrial Training-II: The students are advised to undergo 6-8 weeks training in industry/ Skill Knowledge Provider (SKP)/ Sector Skill Council (SSC) during summer vacation and should submit training report for evaluation during the Third semester and credits will be posted during third semester.

BUILDING CONSTRUCTION

Paper Code: ETVCT-501 L T/P C

Paper: Building Construction 3 1 4

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites: Well versed with salient features of site selection, building bye-laws, types of foundations & their suitability, concept of masonry and types, significance and details of floors, lintels & arches, roofs, stairs, damp-proofing, surface finishes, building planning and services, seismic planning and interior design. To have exposure about various components of buildings as required in construction engineering. Urge to thrive and learn and commonsense are pre requisites.

Learning outcomes: The students should be able to visualize the concepts of different components buildings. Ability to perform the task of supervising construction of buildings will be improved. This subject helps in better understanding of the various subjects of this course in later stages.

UNIT-I

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Definition of a building, classification of buildings based on occupancy, Site selection: Factors to be considered for selection of site for residential, commercial, industrial and public building, Components of building, arrangement of doors, windows, cupboards etc. for residential building. Concept of foundation and its purpose, Types of foundations-shallow and deep; suitability and use of - Spread foundations, stepped foundation, masonry pillars and concrete columns, raft foundation, combined footing. Thumb rules for depth and width of foundation and thickness of concrete block. Pile foundations; their suitability, classification of piles according to function, material and installation of concrete piles (undreamed, bored, compacted).

UNIT-II

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Masonry, brick masonry-Definition of terms: mortar, bond, facing, backing, hearting, column, pillar, jambs, reveals, soffit, plinth, plinth masonry, header, stretcher, bed of brick, bat, queen closer, king closer, frog and quoin, Bond-meaning and necessity; English bond; Bond only 1, 1-1/2 and 2 Brick thick walls in English Bond. T, X and right-angled corner junctions Thickness for 1, 1-1/2 and 2 Brick square pillars in English bond. Construction of Brick Walls-Method of laying bricks in walls, precautions observed in the construction of walls, method of bonding new brick work with old (Toothing, raking back and block bonding) Construction, expansion and contraction joints; purpose and constructional details. Stone Masonry, glossary of terms-Natural bed, bedding planes, string course, corbel, cornice, block-

in course, grouting, mouldings, templates, throating, through stones, parapet, coping, pilaster and buttress. Types of stone Masonry: Rubble Masonry: random and coarsed, Ashlar Masonry: Ashlar fine, Ashlar rough, Ashler facing, specifications for coarsed rubble masonry, principles to be observed in construction of stone masonry walls. Surface Finishes: different types, preparations and applications of plastering, pointing, painting, white washing and curing. Damp Proofing: Dampness: sources, causes and its ill effects, Damp proofing materials and their specifications, Methods of damp proofing: basement, ground floors, plinth and walls, special damp proofing arrangements in bathrooms, WC and kitchen, roofs and window sills, Plinth protection and aprons.

UNIT-III

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Purpose and Classification of walls- load bearing, non-load bearing, dwarf, retaining, breast walls and partition walls. Classification of walls as per materials of construction: brick, stone, reinforced brick, reinforced concrete, precast, hollow and solid concrete block and composite masonry walls. Partition walls: Constructional details, suitability and uses of brick and wooden partition walls. Scaffolding: Constructional details and suitability of mason's brick layers and tubular scaffolding. Meaning and use of arches and lintels: Glossary of terms used in arches and lintels – abutment, pier, arch ring, intrados, soffit, extrados, voussoiers, springer, springing line, crown, key stone, skew back, span, rise, depth of an arch, haunch, spandril, jambs, bearing, thickness of lintel, effective span. Arches: Types of Arches – Semi-circular, segmental, elliptical and parabolic, flat, inverted and relieving. Stone arches and their construction, brick arches and their construction. Doors and Windows: - Glossary of Terms used in Doors and windows, Doors – name, uses and Types: metal doors, ledged and

battened doors, ledged, battened and braced door, framed and panelled doors, glazed and panelled doors, flush doors, collapsible doors, rolling steel shutters, side sliding doors, door frames, PVC shutters and metal doors, Window-names, uses and Types: metal windows, fully panelled windows, fully glazed windows, casement windows, fanlight windows and ventilators, sky light window frames, louvered shutters (emphasis shall be given for using metals and plastics etc. in place of timber).

UNIT-IV

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Floors, Ground floors- glossary of terms: floor finish, topping, under layer, base course, rubble filling, dado and their purpose. Types of floor finishes –cast-in-situ, concrete flooring (monolithic, bonded) Terrazzo flooring, Stone flooring(marble/Granite), Timber flooring, PVC floor, ceramic floor description with sketches and the methods of construction of the floors and their specifications, floor polishing. Upper floors- flooring on RCC slab, Maintenance of floors. Types of roofs, concept of flat, pitched, arched and cell roofs, Glossary of terms for pitched roofs – Various types of Trusses: Timber and steel, batten, eaves, barge, fascia board, gable hip, lap, purlin, rafter, rag bolt, valley, ridge, etc. Stairs- Glossary of terms: different means of access to various floor, stair case, winders, landing, stringer, newel, baluster, riser, tread, width of staircase, hand rail, nosing, etc. Planning and layout of staircase: Relations between rise and tread, determination of width of stair, landing etc. Various types of layout-straight flight, dog legged, open well, quarter turn, half turn (newel and geometrical stairs), bifurcated stair, spiral stair. Introduction to anti-termite measures;

building services; earthquakes: Magnitude and intensity, seismic zoning, seismograph, Precautions to be observed in the design of earthquake prone buildings.

Text Book(s):

[T1] Shushil Kumar, “Building Construction”, Standard Publication

[T2] Arora, S.P. and Bindra, S.P.; “A Text Book of Building Construction”; DhanptRai and Sons, New Delhi

References Book (s):

[R1] P.C.Varghese, “Building Construction”, PHI Publications

[R2] Gurucharan Singh: “Building Construction Technology & Materials”, Standard Book House

[R3] M.L. Gambhir and NehaJamwal, “Building and Construction Materials”, Mc-Graw Hill

[R4] Moorthy, NKR; “A Text Book of Building Construction”, Poona, Engineering Book Publishing Co

[R5] Rangwala, SC: “Building Construction”; Anand, Charotar Book Stall/ Publishing House

SURVEYING I

Paper Code: ETVCT-503 L T/P C

Paper: Surveying-I 3 1 4

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites: The students should have basic knowledge of understanding of building components. To learn the basic concept of surveying, study and understand the types of surveying and its applications in Civil Engineering. To have exposure about chain surveying, compass surveying, leveling and plane tabling as required in field.

Learning outcomes: The students should be able to visualize the concepts of different types of surveying. To perform surveying work individually. Well versed with computations of traversing, plotting, adjustments as required. Well conversant with levelling operation and calculations. Able to perform surveying projects in the field. Helpful in performing survey work in the construction projects such as: detailed surveying, plotting of survey data, preparation of survey maps and setting out works.

UNIT-I

[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]

Introduction and concept of surveying, purpose and objective of surveying, classification of surveying, basic principles of surveying, measurements-linear and angular, units of measurements, Instruments used for taking these measurements. Chain surveying: Introduction, technical terminology (chaining, ranging, offsetting, leader, follower, different points, different lines, different sketches etc.) principle of chain surveying purpose of chain

surveying, advantages and disadvantages. Instruments: - types, construction, working and tests & adjustments. Methodology: Field procedure & operations- chaining, ranging and offsetting in different cases; recording and plotting. Obstacles in chaining, ranging and both, solutions to obstacles. Errors in chain surveying and corrections, traversing by chain surveying- recording and plotting.

UNIT-II

[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]

Compass surveying: Introduction and purpose of compass surveying, principle of compass surveying. Concept of meridian, types of meridians; concept of bearing, different types of bearing; systems of bearing; forward bearing and backward bearing, systems of bearing- WCB & QB. Magnetic dip and declination, isogonics, agonic and isoclinic lines; Local attraction- definition, causes, detection, elimination; Types of compass- construction, working. Use of prismatic compass: Setting and taking observations. Traversing by compass: - different types, field procedure, recording, plotting, checks, closing error and its adjustment; Errors in compass surveying. Numerical problems shall be solved on systems of bearing, declination, local attraction and traversing.

UNIT-III

[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]

Purpose of leveling, concept of a level surface, horizontal surface, vertical surface, datum, MSL, station, gradient, reduced level, bench marks, line of collimation, axis of the bubble tube, axis of the telescope, vertical axis, back sight, foresight, intermediate sight, change point etc. Types of levels, Identification of various parts, uses, advantages and disadvantages of Dumpy level & Auto level. Leveling staff-single piece, folding, invar precision and telescopic. Temporary adjustments and permanent adjustment of dumpy level.

Methods of computing reduced levels-Height of Instrument method and rise and fall method (Arithmetic checks, problem on reduction of levels). Types of leveling:- simple leveling, Differential leveling, Fly leveling, check leveling, profile leveling (Longitudinal-section & cross-section) and reciprocal leveling. Errors in leveling and permissible limits.

UNIT-IV

[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]

Plane Table Surveying- Introduction and purpose of plane table surveying, principle of plane table surveying, study of plane table and its accessories used in plane table survey. Field operations/ procedure: - Setting up of a plane table, Centering, Leveling, marking North direction, Orientation (back sighting & trough compass).

Methods of plane table surveying: Radiation, Intersection, Traversing and Resection. Resection: - Concept of Two point and Three point problems (Concept only). Errors, precautions, advantages and disadvantages of plane table surveying. Introduction to the odolite and total station- uses and applications.

Text Book(s):

[T1] N.N. Basak "Surveying and Leveling" Tata McGraw Hill Publications, New Delhi

[T2] Punmia, B.C.; "Surveying and Leveling", Delhi Standard Publishers Distributors.

[T3] Subramanian, R., "Fundamentals of Surveying and Leveling", Oxford University Press

References Books:

[R1] K.R. Arora, Surveying Vol. I and II Standard Book House, New Delhi

- [R2] Arthur Bannister, “Surveying”, Pearson Education
 [R3] Mimi Das Saikia, Madan Mohan Das, “Surveying”, PHI Publications
 [R4] S.K. Roy, “Fundamentals of Surveying”, PHI Publications
 [R5] T. P. Kanetkar and Kulkarni, “Surveying and Leveling”, Standard Publishers
 [R6] C. Venkatramaiah, “Textbook of Surveying”, 2nd Edition, University Press.

COMMUNICATION SKILLS (Common to All Disciplines)

Paper Code: ETVHS-519 L T/P C Paper: Communication Skills : 2 1 3
 INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS: MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be of 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites: Students should have studied General English up to secondary level and the subject aims at developing communication skills in writing, speaking as well as body language.

Learning Outcomes: The students should be able to communicate effectively to his/her superiors as well as juniors at work place in his/her professional field.

UNIT-I [T1, T2][No. of Hrs. 08]

Recognizing and Understanding Communication Styles: What is Communication?, Passive Communication, Aggressive Communication, Passive-Aggressive Communication, Assertive Communication, Verbal and Non Verbal Communication, Barriers and Gateways to Communication.

UNIT-II [T1, T2][No. of Hrs. 12]

Listening Skills: Types of Listening (theory /definition), Tips for Effective Listening Academic Listening- (lecturing), Listening to Talks and Presentations, Basics of Telephone communication

Writing Skills: Standard Business letter, Report writing, Email drafting and Etiquettes, Preparing Agenda and writing minutes for meetings, Making notes on Business conversations, Effective use of SMS, Case writing and Documentation.

UNIT-III [T1, T2][No. of Hrs. 10]

Soft Skills: Empathy (Understanding of someone else point of view), Intrapersonal skills, Interpersonal skills, Negotiation skills, Cultural Aspects of Communication.

UNIT-IV

[T1,T2][No. of Hrs. 12]

Group Communication: The Basics of Group Dynamics, Group Interaction and Communication, How to Be Effective in Groups, Handling Miscommunication, Handling Disagreements and Conflicts, Constructive Criticism.

Text Books:

[T1] Mckay, M., Davis, M. & Fanning, P.(2008). Messages: The Communication Skills Book, New Harbinger Publications

[T2] Perkins, P.S., & Brown, L. (2008). The Art and Science of Communication: Tools for effective communication in the workplace, John Wiley and Sons

Reference Books:

[R1] Krizan et al (2010). Effective Business Communication, Cengage Learning.

[R2] Scot, O. (2009). Contemporary Business Communication, Biztantra, New Delhi.

[R3] Chaney & Martin (2009). Intercultural Business Communication, Pearson Education

[R4] Penrose et al (2009). Business Communication for Managers, Cengage Learning.

APPLIED MECHANICS

Paper Code: ETVME-501 L T/P C

Paper: Applied Mechanics 3 0 3

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites:

The subject Applied Mechanics deals with basic concepts of mechanics like laws of forces, moments, friction, centre of gravity, laws of motion and simple machines which are required to the students for further understanding of other applied subjects. To introduce the concepts of rigid body mechanics for bodies at rest and in motion to students. To make the students appreciate the applications of basic laws of physics to a variety of problems. Inculcating and enhancing analytical skills to solve numerical problems. Upon the completion of course student should be able to understand the importance of mechanics in engineering and various concepts.

Learning outcomes:

Students will be able to state the relevant laws and apply them to numerical problems. Students will be able to draw free-body diagrams for a given problem and get the required solution. Students will be able to visualize the applications of basic laws in solving numerical problems. Students will be able to correlate the concepts learnt in the relevant courses of higher classes.

UNIT-I:**[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]**

Introduction- Concept of mechanics and applied mechanics – Explanation of mechanics and applied Mechanics, its importance and necessity, giving suitable examples on bodies at rest and in motion, explanation of branches of this subject.

Laws of Forces- Force and its effects. Units and measurement of force. Characteristics of force vector representation. Bow's notation. Types of forces, action and reaction, tension & thrust. Force systems: Coplanar and space force systems. Coplanar, concurrent and non-concurrent forces. Free body diagrams. Resultant and components of forces, concept of equilibrium; parallelogram law of forces. Equilibrium of two forces, super-position and transmissibility of forces, Newton's third law, triangle law of forces, different cases of concurrent coplanar, two forces systems, extension of parallelogram law and triangle law to many forces acting at one point-polygon law of forces, method of resolution into orthogonal components for finding the resultant, graphical methods, special case of three concurrent, coplanar forces, Lami's theorem.

UNIT-II:**[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]**

Moments- Concept of moment, Varignon's theorem – statement only. Principle of moments – application of moments to simple mechanism. Parallel forces, like and unlike parallel forces, calculation of their resultant, concept of couple, moving a force parallel to its line of action, general cases of coplanar force system, general conditions of equilibrium of bodies under coplanar parallel forces.

Friction- Concept of friction, laws of friction, limiting friction and coefficient of friction, sliding friction and rolling friction, inclined plane.

UNIT-III:**[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 12]**

Centre of Gravity and Centroid- Concept of gravity, gravitational force, Centroid and centre of gravity. Centroid for regular lamina and center of gravity for regular solids. Position of centre of gravity of compound bodies and centroid of composite area. CG of bodies and areas with portions removed.

Moment of Inertia of Plane Areas- Concept of Moment of Inertia and second moment of area and Radius of gyration, theorems of parallel and perpendicular axes, second moment of area of common geometrical sections: rectangle, triangle, circle (without derivations). Second moment of area for L, T and I sections. Section modulus without derivation.

UNIT-IV [T1],**T2, T3][No. of Hours: 10]**

Laws of Motion- Concept of momentum, Newton's laws of motion, their application, derivation of force equation from second law of motion, numerical problems on second law of motion, piles, lifts, bodies tied with

string, Newton's third law of motion numerical problems, conservation of momentum, impulse and impulsive force (definition only).

Simple Lifting Machines- Concept of machine, mechanical advantage, velocity ratio and efficiency of a machine, their relationship, law of machine, simple machines (lever, wheel and axle, pulleys, jacks winch crabs only).

Text Book(s):

- [T1] A.K.Tayal, “Engineering Mechanics: Statics and Dynamics”, Umesh publications
[T2] R.K. Rajput, “Applied Mechanics”, Lakshmi Publications
[T3] A. K. Upadhyay, “Applied Mechanics, Kataria Publications

References Book(s):

- [R1] Beer and Johnston, “Mechanics for Engineers (Statics and Dynamics)”, McGraw Hill Co. Ltd.
[R2] R. S. Khurmi, “Applied Mechanics”, S. Chand publications
[R3] Hibbeler R C, “Engineering Mechanics: Statics, Low Price Edition”, Pearson Education
[R4] Hibbeler R C, “Engineering Mechanics: Dynamics, Low Price Edition”, Pearson Education
[R5] Timoshenko, S.P., and Young, D.H., “Engineering Mechanics”, McGraw Hill international
[R6] V.S. Mokashi, “Engineering Mechanics Vol. I and II”, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co. ltd., New Delhi

APPLIED MATHEMATICS

(Open Elective-I)

Paper Code: ETVAS-507 L T/P C Paper: Applied Mathematics 3 0 3
INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS: MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Objective:

The objective of the paper is to facilitate the student with the basics of Applied Mathematics that are required for an engineering student.

UNIT- I

[T1], [T2][No. of hrs. 12]

Successive differentiation: Leibnitz theorem for nth derivative (without proof). Infinite series: Convergence and divergence of infinite series, positive terms infinite series, necessary condition, comparison test (Limit test), D’Alembert ratio test, Integral Test, Cauchy’s root test, Raabe’s test and Logarithmic test(without proof). Alternating series, Leibnitz test, conditional and absolutely convergence. Taylor’s and Maclaurin’s expansion(without proof) of function (e^x , $\log(1+x)$, $\cos x$, $\sin x$) with remainder terms, Taylor’s and Maclaurin’s series, Error and approximation.

UNIT- II

[T1], [T2][No. of hrs. 12]

Asymptotes to Cartesian curves. Radius of curvature and curve tracing for Cartesian, parametric and polar curves. Integration: integration using reduction formula for $\int \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}}$. Application of integration : Area under the curve, length of the curve, volumes and surface area of solids of revolution about axis only. Gamma and Beta functions.

UNIT- III

[T1], [T2][No. of hrs. 12]

Matrices: Orthogonal matrix, Hermitian matrix, Skew-Hermitian matrix and Unitary matrix. Inverse of matrix by Gauss-Jordan Method (without proof). Rank of matrix by echelon and Normal (canonical) form. Linear dependence and linear independence of vectors. Consistency and inconsistency of linear system of homogeneous and non homogeneous equations. Eigen values and Eigen vectors. Properties of Eigen values (without proof). Cayley-Hamilton theorem (without proof). Diagonalization of matrix. Quadratic form, reduction of quadratic form to canonical form.

UNIT-IV

[T1], [T2][No. of hrs. 12]

Ordinary differential equations: First order linear differential equations, Leibnitz and Bernoulli's equation. Exact differential equations, Equations reducible to exact differential equations. Linear differential equation of higher order with constant coefficients, Homogeneous and non homogeneous differential equations reducible to linear differential equations with constant coefficients. Method of variation of parameters. Bessel's and Legendre's equations (without series solutions), Bessel's and Legendre's functions and their properties.

Text:

[T1] B. S. Grewal, "Higher Engineering Mathematics", Khanna Publications.

[T2] R. K. Jain and S.R. K. Iyengar, "Advanced Engineering Mathematics", Narosa Publications.

References:

[R1] E. Kresyzig, "Advance Engineering Mathematics", Wiley publications

[R2] G. Hadley, "Linear Algebra", Narosa Publication

[R3] N.M. Kapoor, "A Text Book of Differential Equations", Pitambar Publication.

[R4] Wylie R, "Advance Engineering Mathematics", Tata McGraw-Hill

[R5] Schaum's Outline on Linear Algebra, Tata McGraw-Hill

[R6] Polking and Arnold, "Ordinary Differential Equation using MATLAB", Pearson.

HUMAN VALUES & PROFESSIONAL ETHICS

(General Elective-I)

Paper Code: ETVHS-513 L T/P C

Paper : Human Values & Professional Ethics 2 1 2

Non-University Examination Scheme (NUES)

Note: There will be no End-Term External University Examination. Marks are to be given on the basis of two internal sessional test of 30 marks each and one final Viva-voce project report Examination of 40 marks.

Objectives:

This introductory course input is intended

- a. To help the students appreciate the essential complementarity between ‘VALUES’ and ‘SKILLS’ to ensure sustained happiness and prosperity which are the core aspirations of all human beings.
- b. To facilitate the development of a holistic perspective among students towards life, profession and happiness, based on the correct understanding of the Human reality and the rest of the Existence. Such a Holistic perspective forms the basis of value-based living in a natural way.
- c. To highlight plausible implications of such a Holistic understanding in terms of ethical human conduct, trustful and mutually satisfying human behaviour and mutually enriching interaction with Nature.

UNIT-1: Introduction to Value Education **[T1], [R1], [R4][No. of Hrs. 07]**

1. Understanding the need, basic guidelines, content and process for value education.
2. Basic Human Aspirations: Prosperity and happiness
3. Methods to fulfil the human aspirations – understanding and living in harmony at various levels.
4. Practice Session – 1.

UNIT-2: Harmony in the Human Being **[T2], [R1],[R2][No. of Hrs. 08]**

1. Co-existence of the sentient “I” and the material body–understanding their needs–Happiness & Conveniences.
2. Understanding the Harmony of “I” with the body–Correct appraisal of physical needs and the meaning of prosperity.
3. Programme to ensure harmony of “I” and Body-Mental and Physical health and happiness.
4. Harmony in family and society: Understanding Human-human relationship in terms of mutual trust and respect.
5. Understanding society and nation as extensions of family and society respectively.
6. Practice Session – 02

UNIT-3: Basics of Professional Ethics **[T1],[R4]][No. of Hrs. 07]**

1. Ethical Human Conduct – based on acceptance of basic human values.

2. Humanistic Constitution and universal human order – skills, sincerity and fidelity.
3. To identify the scope and characteristics of people – friendly and eco-friendly production system, Technologies and management systems.
4. Practice Session – 03.

UNIT-4: Professional Ethics in practice [T1], [T2], [T3], [R3][No. of Hrs. 08]

1. Profession and Professionalism – Professional Accountability, Roles of a professional, Ethics and image of profession.
2. Engineering Profession and Ethics - Technology and society, Ethical obligations of Engineering professionals, Roles of Engineers in industry, society, nation and the world.
3. Professional Responsibilities – Collegiality, Loyalty, Confidentiality, Conflict of Interest, Whistle Blowing
4. Practice Session – 04

Text Books:

- [T1] Professional Ethics, R. Subramanian, Oxford University Press.
- [T2] Professional Ethics & Human Values: SubhashBhalchandraGogate, Vikas publication
- [T3] Professional Ethics & Human Values: Prof. D.R. Kiran, TATA McGraw Hill Education.
- [T4] Professional Ethics & Human Values: S.B. Srivasthva, SciTech Publications (India) Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.

References:

- [R1] Success Secrets for Engineering Students: Prof. K.V. SubbaRaju, Ph.D., Published by SMARTstudent.
- [R2] Ethics in Engineering Mike W. Martin, Department of Philosophy, Chapman University and Roland Schinzing, School of Engineering, University of California, Irvine.
- [R3] Human Values: A. N. Tripathy (2003, New Age International Publishers)
- [R4] Value Education website, <http://www.universalhumanvalues.info>[16]
- [R5] Fundamentals of Ethics, Edmond G. Seebauer& Robert L. Barry, Oxford University Press.
- [R6] Human Values and Professional Ethics: R. R. Gaur, R. Sangal and G. P. Bagaria, Eecel Books (2010, New Delhi). Also, the Teachers’ Manual by the same author.

*PRACTICAL SESSIONS OF 14 HOME ASSIGNMENTS will be followed by the students pursuing this paper. (Ref: Professional Ethics & Human Values: S.B. Srivastava, SciTech Publications (India) Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.)

CONTENT OF PRACTICE SESSION

Module 1: Course Introduction – Needs, Basic Guidelines, Content and Process of Value Education

PS-1: Imagine yourself in detail. What are the goals of your life? How do you set your goals in your life? How do you differentiate between right and wrong? What have been your achievements and shortcoming in your life? Observe and analyze them.

Expected Outcome:

The students start exploring themselves; get comfortable to each other and to the teacher and start finding the need and relevance for the course.

PS-2: Now a days there is lot of voice about techno-genie maladies such as energy and natural resource depletion, environmental Pollution, Global Warming, Ozone depletion, Deforestation, etc. – all these scenes are man-made problems threatening the survival of life on the earth – what is root cause of these maladies and what is the way out in your opinion?

On the other hand there is rapidly growing danger because of nuclear proliferation, arm race, terrorism, criminalization of politics, large scale corruption, scams, breakdown of relationships, generation gap, depression and suicidal attempts, etc - what do you think the root cause of these threats to human happiness and peace – what could be the way out in your opinion?

Expected Outcome:

The students start finding out that technical education with study of human values can generate more solutions than problems They also start feeling that lack of understanding of human values is the root cause of all the problems and the sustained solution could emerge only through understanding of human values and value based living. Any solutions brought out through fear, temptation or dogma will not be sustainable.

PS-3:1. Observe that each one of us has Natural Acceptance, based on which one can verify right or not right for him. Verify this in case of following:

- a) What is naturally acceptable to you in relationship – feeling of respect or disrespect?
- b) What is naturally acceptable to you - to nurture or to exploit others? Is your living the same as your natural acceptance or different?
2. Out of three basic requirements for fulfillment of your aspirations, right understanding, relationship and physical facilities, observe how the problems in your family are related to each. Also observe how much time and efforts you devote for each in your daily routine.

Expected Outcome:

1. The students are able to see that verification on the basis of natural acceptance and experiential validation through living is the only way to verify the right or wrong, and referring to any external source life text or instrument or any other person cannot enable them to verify with authenticity, it will only develop assumptions.
2. The students are able to see that their practice in living is not in harmony with their natural acceptance at most of the time, and all they need to do is to refer to their natural acceptance to remove this disharmony.
3. The students are able to see that lack of right understanding leading to lack of relationship is the major cause of the problems in their family and the lack of physical facilities in most of the cases; while they have given higher priority to earning of physical facilities in their life ignoring relationship and not being aware that right understanding is the most important requirement for any human being.

Module 2: Understanding harmony in human being – Harmony in myself!

PS-4: Prepare the list of your desires. Observe whether the desires are related with self “I” or body. If it appears to be related with the both, see which part of it is related to self “I” and which part is related to body.

Expected Outcome:

The students are able to see that they can enlist their desires and the desires are not vague, also they are able to relate their desires to “I” and “body” distinctly. If, any desire appears to be related with both, they are able to see that feeling is related to “I” while the physical facility is related to the body. They are also able to see that “I” and “body” are two realities, and most of their desires are related to “I” and not with the “Body”; while their efforts are mostly connected on the fulfillment of the need of the body assuming that it will meet the needs of “I” too.

PS-5:

1. {A}. Observe that any physical facilities you use, follows the given sequence with time; Necessary and tasteful – unnecessary & tasteful – unnecessary & tasteless.
{B}. In contrast, observe that any feelings in you are either naturally acceptable or not acceptable at all. If, naturally acceptable, you want it continuously and if not acceptable, you do not want it at any moment.
2. List Down all your activities. Observe whether the activity is of “I” or of “body” or with the participation both “I” and “body”.
3. Observe the activities with “I”. Identify the object of your attention for different moments (over a period say 5 to 10 minute) and draw a line diagram connecting these points. Try to observe the link between any two nodes.

Expected Outcome:

1. The students are able to see that all physical facilities they use are required for limited time in a limited quantity. Also they are able to see that cause of feeling, they want continuity of the naturally acceptable feelings and they do not want feelings which are not naturally acceptable eve for a single moment.
2. The students are able to see that activities like understanding, desires, thoughts and selection are the activities of “I” only; the activities like breathing, palpitation of different parts of the body are fully the activities of the body. With the acceptance of “I”, while activities they do with their sense organs like hearing through ears, seeing through eyes, sensing through touch, tasting through tongue and smelling through nose or the activities they do with their work organs like hands, legs, etc. are such activities that require the participation of both “I” and “body”
3. The students become aware of their activities of “I” and start finding their focus of attention at different moments. Also they are able see that most of their desires are coming from outsides (through preconditioning or sensation) and are not based on their natural acceptance.

PS-6: 1.Chalk out the program to ensure that you are responsible to your body – for the nurturing, protection and right utilization of the body.

2. Find out the plants and shrubs growing in and your campus. Find out their use for curing different diseases.

Expected Outcome:

The students are able to list down activities related to a proper upkeep of the body and practice them in their daily routine. They are also able to appreciate the plants wildy growing in and around the campus which can be beneficial in curing the different diseases.

Module 3: Understanding harmony in the family and society - Harmony in Human – Human relationship

PS-7: Form small groups in the class and in that group initiate the dialogue and ask the eight questions related to trust. The eight questions are-

Let each student answer the question for himself and everyone else. Discuss the difference between intention and competence.

Expected Outcome:

The students are able to see that the first four questions are related to our natural acceptance i.e. intention and the next four to our competence. They are able to note that the intention is always correct, only competence is lacking. We generally evaluate ourselves on the basis of our intention and other on the basis of their competence. We seldom look at our competence and other's intention as a result we conclude that I am a good person and other is a bad person.

PS-8:

1. Observe that on how many occasions you are respecting your related ones (by doing the right evaluation) and on how many occasion you are disrespecting by way of under evaluation, over evaluation or otherwise evaluation.
2. Also observe whether your feeling of respect is based on treating the other as yourself or on differentiations based on body, physical facilities or beliefs.

Expected Outcome:

The students are able to see that respect is right evaluation and only right evaluation leads to fulfilment of relationship. Many present problems in the society are an outcome of differentiation (lack of understanding of respect) like gender biasness, generation gap, caste conflicts, class struggle, and domination through poor play, communal violence, and clash of isms and so on so forth.

All these problems can be solved by realizing that the other is like me as he has the same natural acceptance, potential and program to ensure a happy and prosperous life for him and for others though he may have different body, physical facilities or beliefs.

PS-9:

1. Write a note in the form of a story, poem, skit, essay, narration, dialogue, to educate a child.

Evaluate it in a group.

2. Develop three chapters to introduce “social science”, its needs, scope and content in the primary education of children.

Expected Outcome:

The students are able to use their creativity for educating children. The students are able to see that they can play a role in providing value education for children. They are able to put in simple words the issues that are essential to understand for children and comprehensible to them. The students are able to develop an outline of holistic model for social science and compare it with the existing model.

Module 4: Understanding harmony in the nature and existence – Whole existence as Co – existence -

PS-10: Prepare the list of units (things) around you. Classify them into four orders. Observe and explain the mutual fulfilment of each unit with other orders.

Expected Outcome:

The students are able to differentiate between the characteristics and activities of different orders and study the mutual fulfilment among them. They are also able to see that human beings are not fulfilling to their orders today and need to take appropriate steps to ensure right participation (in term of nurturing, protection and right utilization) in the nature.

PS-11:

1. Make a chart for the whole existence. List down different courses of studies and relate them to different or levels in the existence.
2. Choose any one subject being taught today. Evaluate and suggest suitable modifications to make it appropriate and holistic.

Expected Outcome:

The students are confident that they can understand the whole existence; nothing is a mystery in this existence. They are also able to see the interconnectedness in the nature, and point out how different courses of study relate to the different units and levels. Also they are liable to make out how these courses can be made appropriate and holistic.

Module 5: Implication of the above Holistic Understanding of Harmony at all Levels of Existence.

PS-12: Choose any two current problem of different kind in the society and suggest how they can be solved on the basis of the natural acceptance of human values. Suggest the steps you will take in present conditions.

Expected Outcome:

The students are liable to present sustainable solutions to the problem in society and nature. They are also able to see that these solutions are practicable and draw road maps to achieve them.

PS-13:

1. Suggest ways in which you can use your knowledge of engineering / technology / management for universal human order from your family to world family.
2. Suggest one format of humanistic constitution at the level of nation from your side.

Expected Outcome:

The students are able to grasp the right utilization of their knowledge in their streams of technology / engineering / management to ensure mutually enriching and recyclable production systems.

PS-14: The course is going to be over now. Evaluate your state before and after the course in terms of-

- Thoughts
- Behavior
- Work and
- Realization

Do you have any plan to participate in the transition of the society after graduating from the institute? Write a brief note on it.

Expected Outcome:

The students are able to sincerely evaluate the course and share with their friends. They are also able to suggest measures to make the course more effective and relevant. They are also able to make use of their understanding in the course for happy and prosperous society.

**LIFE SKILLS)
(General Elective-I)**

Paper Code: ETVHS-515 L T/P C

Paper: Life Skills 202

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS:

75

-
1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
 2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be of 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites: Students should have studied subjects such as General languages, social studies and Moral education at school level. The objective of this subject is to prepare the students to become a good citizen and a professional useful to the society.

Learning Outcomes: The knowledge of this subject will give the student a value system which will help him in taking decisions in professional and social life for the benefit of society at large.

UNIT-I

[T1,T2][No. of Hrs. 07]

Introduction: Definition and importance of Life Skills, Livelihood Skills, Survival Skills, Life Skills Approach, Life Skills based education, Life Skills Training- Implementation Models

UNIT-II

[T1,T2][No. of Hrs. 08]

Learning and Performance, Cognitive Development, Maturation, Adult Learning, Approaches to Learning Pillars of Education and Life Skills- Four Pillars: Learning to Know, Learning to Do, Learning to Live Together, Learning to be learning throughout Life

UNIT-III

[T1,T2][No. of Hrs. 08]

Social Skills and Negotiation Skills: Self Awareness, Empathy, Effective Communication, Interpersonal Relationships

Thinking Skills: Nature, Element of Thought, Types, Concept Formation, Reasoning, Creative and Critical Thinking

UNIT-IV

[T1,T2][No. of Hrs. 07]

Coping Skills: Coping with Emotions, Coping with Stress, Integrated use of thinking skills, social skills and coping skills

Text Books:

- [T1] Rajasenan, N.V. (2010). Life Skills, Personality and Leadership, Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development, TamilNadu
- [T2] Duffy, Grover,K., Eastwood, A. (2008). Psychology for Living-Adjustment, Growth and Behavior Today, Pearson Education

Reference Books:

- [R1] Debra McGregor, (2007), “Developing Thinking; Developing Learning - A Guide to Skills in Education”, Open University Press, New York, USA
- [R2] Singh Madhu, (2003). “Understanding Life Skills, Background paper prepared for Education for All: The Leap to Equality”
- [R3] Nair. A. Radhakrishnan, (2010). “Life Skills Training for Positive Behaviour”, Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development, Tamil Nadu.
- [R4] Dahama O.P., Bhatnagar O.P, (2005). “Education and Communication for Development, (2nd Ed.)”, Oxford& IBH Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi

**PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT & BEHAVIORAL SCIENCE (From
USMS)
(General Elective-I)**

Paper Code: ETVHS-517 L T/P C

Paper: Personality Development & Behavioral Science 202

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be of 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites:

Students should have studied subjects such as General languages, social studies and Moral education at school level. The objective of this subject is to prepare the students to become a good citizen and a professional useful to the society.

Learning Outcomes:

The knowledge of this subject will give the student a value system which will help him in taking decisions in professional and social life for the benefit of society at large.

UNIT-I

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs. 07]

Definition and Basics of Personality, Understanding Traits and Types of Personality, Analyzing strength and weakness (SW), Body Language

UNIT-II

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs. 08]

Business Etiquettes and Public Speaking: Business Manners. Body Language Gestures, Email and Net Etiquettes, Etiquette of the Written Word, Etiquettes on the Telephone, Handling Business Meetings; Introducing Characteristic, Model Speeches, Role Play on Selected Topics with Case Analysis and Real Life Experiences.

UNIT-III

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs. 08]

How to Make a Presentation, the Various Presentation Tools, along with Guidelines of Effective Presentation, Boredom Factors in Presentation and How to Overcome them, Interactive Presentation & Presentation as Part of a Job Interview, Art of Effective Listening.

Resume Writing Skills, Guidelines for a Good Resume, How to Face an Interview Board, Proper Body Posture, Importance of Gestures and Steps to Succeed in Interviews. Practice Mock Interview in Classrooms with Presentations on Self; Self Introduction – Highlighting Positive and Negative Traits and Dealing with People with Face to Face.

UNIT-IV

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs. 07]

Coping Management, Working on Attitudes: Aggressive, Assertive and Submissive Coping with Emotions, Coping with Stress

Text Books:

- [T1] McGraw, S. J., (2008), “Basic Managerial Skills for All, Eighth Edition”, Prentice Hall of India.
- [T2] The Results-Driven Manager (2005). Business Etiquette for the New Workplace: The Results-Driven Manager Series (Harvard Results Driven Manager)

Reference Books:

- [R1] Pease, A. & Pease, B. (2006)., “The Definitive Book of Body Language”, Bantam Books.
- [R2] Scannell, E. & Rickenbacher, C. (2010)., “The Big Book of People Skills Games: Quick, Effective Activities for Making Great Impressions, Boosting Problem-Solving Skills and Improving Customer Service”, McGraw Hill Education

APPLIED MECHANICS LAB

Paper Code: ETVCT-551 L T/P C

Paper: Applied Mechanics Lab 0 3 3

List of Experiments:

1. Verification of the laws of polygon of forces.
2. To verify the forces in the different members of a jib crane.
3. To verify the reaction at the supports of a simply supported beam.
4. To find out centre of gravity of regular and irregular laminas.
5. To verify the principle of moments using the bell crank lever apparatus
6. To determine the coefficient of static friction between two surfaces
7. To find moment of inertia of a flywheel
8. To find the mechanical advantage, velocity ratio and efficiency in the case of inclined planes.
9. To find the mechanical advantage, velocity ratio and efficiency in the case of Screw Jack
10. To find the mechanical advantage, velocity ratio and efficiency in the case of worm and worm wheel
11. To find the mechanical advantage, velocity ratio and efficiency in the case of single winch Crab.
12. Graphical solutions for the following problems a. Resultant of Coplanar Non Concurrent force system:
 - i. One problem with resultant as a force
 - ii. One problem with resultant as a couple b. Equilibrium of Coplanar Non Concurrent force system: one Problem c. Friction: One Problem

INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY

This is a gateway subject to remaining course. While imparting theoretical instructions, teachers are expected to demonstrate the various apparatus and related concepts to the students by correlating theory and practical. It is further recommended that more emphasis should be laid in conducting practical work by individual students.

APPLIED MATHEMATICS LAB

Paper Code: ETVAS-557 L T/P C

Paper: Applied Mathematics Lab 0 3 3

Based on theory courses ETVAS-507 (10-12 experiments)

1. Curve fitting using Method of Least squares.
2. Solution of algebraic and transcendental equation using Gauss- Seidal's iteration method.
3. Solution of algebraic and transcendental equation using Finite difference method.
4. Numerical integration using Trapezoidal Rule & Simpson's one third rule.
5. Solution of ordinary differential equations using Runge-Kutta method.
6. Calculation of probability using probability distributions.
7. Calculation of correlation coefficient.
8. Calculation of Numerical measures such as mean, variance, Skewness & Kurtosis.
9. Estimation of mean & variance using sampling & Hypothesis.
10. Calculation of Rank Correlation.
11. Analysis os samples using ANOVA.

BUILDING CONSTRUCTION LAB

Paper Code: ETVCT-551 L T/P C

Paper: Building Construction Lab 0 3 3

List of Experiments:

1. Demonstration of tools and plants used in building construction
2. Study of layout of building
3. To construct brick bonds (English bond only) in one, one and half and two brick thick walls
4. To study and construct English bond for L junction
5. To study and construct English bond for T junction
6. To study and construct English bond for cross junction
7. To study and construct English bond for columns
8. Visit to construction site for showing the construction of foundations
9. Visit to construction site for showing the details of construction of masonry works
10. Visit to construction site for showing the details of Flooring: Laying of flooring on an already prepared lime concrete base

11. Visit to construction site for showing the details of plastering and pointing
12. Visit to construction site for showing the details of White and colour washing
13. Site visit to study Damp proof courses
14. Site visit to study use of special type of shuttering/cranes/heavy machines in construction work
15. Experts may be invited from field/industry for expert lectures

While imparting instructions in this subject, teachers are expected to take students to work site and explain constructional process and special details for various sub-components of a buildings. It is also important to make use of audio visual aids/video films (if available) to show specialized operations. The practical work should be given due importance and efforts should be made that each student should perform practical work independently. For carrying out practical works, institutes shall develop building yard where enough raw materials is made available for students to perform practical work.

SURVEYING I

Paper Code: ETVCT-553 LT/PC

Paper: Surveying-I044

List of Experiments:

1. To study linear measurement instruments
2. Chaining, ranging and off-setting of a survey line
3. To find out the area using offset-survey
4. Traversing using chain surveying
5. To study prismatic compass
6. To measure the angles between the intersecting lines using compass
7. Traversing using chain and compass survey (recording, plotting and adjusting closing error)
8. To study dumpy level and leveling staves
9. To find out the reduced levels of different stations using Height of Instrument (HI) method.
10. To find out the reduced levels of different stations using rise and fall method.
11. To carry out leveling of a small area
12. To study plane table and its accessories
13. To find out the distance between different points using Radiation method
14. To find out the distance between different points using Intersection
15. To conduct plane table traversing

INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY

This is highly practice-oriented course. While imparting theoretical instructions, teachers are expected to demonstrate the use of various instruments in surveying; stress should be laid on correct use of various instruments so as to avoid/minimize errors during surveying. It is further recommended that more emphasis should be laid in conducting practical work by individual students. Technical visit to Survey of India, Northern Region and Great Trigonometrical Survey (GTS), Dehradun may be considered and explored.

VOCATION WORKSHOP-I

(Discipline Specific)

Paper Code: ETVCT-555 L T/PC

Paper: Vocation Workshop-I044

Objectives and Pre-requisites:

To have a balanced overall development of student; To integrate theory with practice; To provide hand on experience about use of different tools and basic manufacturing practices; To develop general manual and machining skills in the students.

Learning outcomes:

Students are able to respect and visualize dignity of labour, precision, safety at work place, team working and development of right attitude.

DETAILED CONTENTS (PRACTICAL EXERCISES)

Note: The students are supposed to come in proper workshop dress prescribed by the institute. Wearing shoes in the workshop(s) is compulsory. Importance of safety and cleanliness, safety measures and upkeep of tools, equipment and environment in each of the following shops should be explained and practiced. The students should prepare sketches of various tools/jobs in their practical Notebook.

1. Carpentry Shop
 1. Preparation of half lap joint
 2. Preparation of Mortise and Tenon Joint
2. Painting Shop
 1. Painting and polishing Practice on wooden items and metallic surfaces
 2. Practice of lettering by brush
3. Fitting Shop
 1. Demonstration & practice of simple operation of hack-sawing, demonstration and description of various types of blades and their specifications, uses and method of fitting the blade.
 2. Marking job, use of marking tools and measuring instruments.
 3. Filing a dimensioned rectangular or square piece of an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\text{mm}$
 4. Drilling practice (production of flat surfaces). Checking by straight edge.
4. Welding Shop

1. Practice of striking arc bending and tacking while using electric arc welding set.
2. Welding practice on electric arc welding for making uniform and straight weld beads and end preparation
3. Preparation of butt joint by gas and arc welding.
4. Preparation of T- joint by using electric arc welding.

References Books:

- [R1] Workshop Technology I, II, III, by S K Hajra, Choudhary and A K Chaoudhary; Media Promoters and Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Bombay
- [R2] Workshop Technology by Manchanda Vol. I,II,III; India Publishing House, Jalandhar.
- [R3] Manual on Workshop Practice by K Venkata Reddy, KL Narayana et al; MacMillan India Ltd. New Delhi
- [R4] Basic Workshop Practice Manual by T Jeyapoovan; Vikas Publishing House (P) Ltd., New Delhi
- [R5] Workshop Technology by B.S. Raghuwansh;,DhanpatRai and Co., New Delhi
- [R6] Workshop Technology by HS Bawa; Tata McGraw Hill Publishers, New Delhi

BUILDING PLANNING AND CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY

Paper Code: ETVCT-502 L T/P C

Paper: Building Planning and Construction Technology 303

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

-
1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
 2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites:

To cover the study of building planning aspects of various residential, commercial and hospital buildings, planning of various projects. To learn and understand building byelaws and their applicability; principles of planning; importance of orientation and CAD; To understand the basics of construction technology; to study the significance of quality and safety; To study the nuances of concrete and concrete technology. To understand different stages of preparation of concrete & significant types of concretes; To study the concept of Non-destructive testing. The pre requisite knowledge on building components and construction is necessary.

Learning outcomes:

After completing this course, student will be able to visualize the concept and applicability of building bye-laws and implement the same in planning and construction. Shall acquire the required planning skills and in a position to suggest plans for various buildings. Enhanced

confidence and understanding of various aspects of construction technology, enables him in making better engineer. Knowledge of concrete, concreting and their types is immensely useful in construction sites. This subject helps in understanding the various subjects of this course in later stages.

UNIT-I

[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]

Building bye-Laws- Introduction, Terminology, Objectives, Floor area ratio (FAR) and Floor space Index (FSI), Principles underlying building byelaws, Minimum plot sizes and building frontage, Open spaces, Minimum standard dimensions of building elements. Provisions for - lighting & ventilation, safety from fire & explosions, means of access, drainage & sanitation and safety of works against hazards or accidents. Requirements for- off street parking, green belt and landscaping, special requirements for low income housing, Sizes of structural elements and Applicability of the bye-laws. Climate and its influence on building planning- Solar radiation, Temperature of air, Wind, Humidity, Precipitation, Climatic zones, Climate and comfort, Earth and its motion, Directions and their characteristics, Landscaping.

UNIT-II

[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]

Principles of Planning of Buildings- Aspect, Prospect, Privacy, Furniture requirement, Roominess, Grouping, Circulation, Sanitation, Lighting, Ventilation, Cleanliness, Flexibility, Elegance, Economy, Practical Considerations.

Orientation Of Buildings- Introduction, Orientation, Factors affecting orientation, Sun, Wind, Rain, C.B.R.I.: Suggestions for obtaining optimum orientation, Orientation criteria for Indian conditions. Economy Measures in Building Construction- General, Economy of land, material of construction, labour, time and money spending. Introduction to Building Drawing and Brief History of Building Drawing, planning of residential buildings and public buildings. Significance of computer aided building drawing- CAD Hardware, CAD Software, AutoCAD, Application of AutoCAD.

UNIT-III

[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]

Fundamentals of Construction Technology- brief introduction to definition and discussions, construction activities and processes, construction workers and estimating; construction scheduling, productivity and mechanization, documents and records, quality, safety and codes & regulations. Site lay out and infrastructure development. Transportation and handling- road, railway, water way and airway. Fabrication of structural steel and erection of steel structures, erection of precast reinforced concrete structures. Quality control and assurance- definitions and introduction to ISO 900 quality systems.

Safety- basic principles on safety, housekeeping, personal safety, fire protection, electrical safety, mechanical handling, transportation, scaffolds & ladders, excavation, formwork and concreting.

UNIT-IV

[T1, T2, T3][No. of Hrs: 11]

Concrete and Concreting- definition of concrete, important properties of concrete both in plastic state and hardened state, Composition and fineness of cement, quality of fine and coarse aggregates, quality of water, use of admixtures, brief idea about- various stages of preparation of concrete, formwork- necessity and selection, materials used. Reinforcing steel,

shotcrete, lightweight & heavyweight concrete, Ready- mixed concrete, fibre reinforced concrete and pre-stressed concrete, inspection and acceptance of finished concrete, Non-Destructive testing of Hardened concrete.

Text Books:

- [T1] Kumara swamy and KameswaraRao, Building Panning and Drawing, Charotar Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- [T2] Dr. H. J. Shah, Building Panning and Drawing, Charotar Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- [T3] Subir K Sarkar, SubhajitSaraswati, Construction Technology, Oxford University Press

References Books:

- [R1] Gambhir, M. L., “Concrete Technology” MacMillan India Ltd., New Delhi
- [R2] Malik, R. S., “Civil Engineering Drawing”, Asia Publishing House
- [R3] Shah, M. G. and Kale, C. M., “Principles of Building Drawing”, MacMillan, Delhi
- [R4] Neville, A. M. and Brooks, J. J., “Concrete Technology”, Pearson Publications

ESTIMATING & COSTING

Paper Code: ETVCT-504 L T/P C

Paper: Estimating & Costing 3 1 4

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites:

Basic knowledge of building construction, surveying are the prerequisites and enhance ability of understanding of the subject. To study concepts of quantity surveying; To learn different types of estimates; to understand analysis of rates of various building operations; to study the details of contracting; to study billing and valuation. To prepare detailed estimate of a building;

Learning outcomes:

Students gain the knowledge of estimating and costing which is an essential requirement of employability. Able to do the quantity surveying work independently. Ability to understand the contracting procedures, billing & valuation aspects further helps in better understanding of intricacies of Civil Engineers role. Improved ability to prepare material estimates for various construction and civil engineering projects.

UNIT-I

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Introduction to quantity surveying/ estimating and its importance.Types of estimates; - Preliminary estimates, Plinth area estimate, Cubic rate estimate and Estimate per unit base.Detailed estimates- Definition- Stages of preparation – details of measurement and calculation of quantities and abstract. Units of measurement for various items of work as per

BIS:1200. Rules for measurements. Different methods of taking out quantities – Centre line method and long wall & short wall method. Preparation of detailed estimate complete with detailed reports, specifications, abstract of cost and material requirement statements for a small residential building with flat roof.

UNIT-II: [T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Analysis of rates: Detailed specifications of different types of building works from excavation to foundations, superstructure and finishing operation.

- A. Steps in the analysis of rates for any item of work: Requirement of materials, labour, sundries, water charges and contractor's profit.
- B. Calculation of quantities of materials for:
 - a. Cement mortars of different proportion
 - b. Cement concrete of different proportion
 - c. Brick/stone masonry in cement mortar
 - d. Plastering and pointing
 - e. White washing, painting
 - f. R.C.C. work in slab, beams.
- C. Analysis of Rates- Steps involved in the analysis of rates. Requirement of material, labour, sundries, contractor's profit and overheads
- (D) Running and maintenance cost of construction equipment.

UNIT-III: [T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Contracting: Meaning of contract, Qualities of a good contractor, Essentials of a contract, Types of contracts, their advantages, disadvantages and suitability, system of payment. Single and two cover-bids; tender, tender forms and documents, tender notice, submission of tender and deposit of earnest money, security deposit, retention money, maintenance period. Types of contracting firms/ construction companies. Introduction to CSR and calculation of cost based on premium on Common Schedule Rates (CSR).

UNIT-IV [T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Billing: Measurement of work for payment of contractors and suppliers. Type of Measurement book, Maintenance of measurement book. Types of payments: First, running, advance, first & final and final payment. Valuation: Purpose of valuation, principles of valuation, Definition of various terms related to valuation like depreciation, sinking fund, salvage and scrap value, market value, fair rent, year's purchase etc. Methods of valuation (i) replacement cost method (ii) rental return method .

INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY

This is an applied engineering subject. Teachers are expected to provide working drawings for various civil engineering works and students be asked to calculate the quantities of materials required for execution of such works. Teachers should conceptualize analysis of rates for different types of works along with valuation of property.

Text Book(s):

[T1] B. N. Dutta- Estimating and costing in Civil Engg, UPSPD.

[T2] M .Chakraborty, “Estimating costing and Specifications in Civil Engg”, Jain Book Depot

Reference Book (s):

[R1] D.S.R. [Delhi Schedule Rates] C.P.W.D

[R2] PWD Account Code

[R3] Samuelson and Nardhaus-Economics, McGraw Hill

[R4] ‘Text book of Estimating and Costing’ by G.S.Birdie

[R5] ‘Civil Engineering Building Drawing’ by Gurucharan Singh

ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE
(Common To all Disciplines)

Paper Code: ETVEN-502 L T/P C

Paper: Environmental Science 3 0 3

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be of 12.5 marks.

Objective:

The objective of this course is to make students environment conscious. They will be exposed through the fundamental concepts of environment and ecosystem so that they can appreciate the importance of individual and collective efforts to preserve and protect our environment. This course must raise various questions in student’s mind that how our environment is inter dependent on various factors and how human being must care for their natural surroundings.

UNIT-I

[T1], [R3] [No. of hrs. 12]

Environmental Studies: Ecosystems, Bio-diversity and its Conservation

- (i) The Multidisciplinary Nature of Environmental Studies

Definition, scope and importance of Environmental Studies, Biotic and a biotic component of environment, need for environmental awareness.

- (ii) Ecosystems

Concept of an ecosystem, structure and function of an ecosystem, producers, consumers and decomposers, energy flow in the ecosystem, ecological succession, food chains, food webs and ecological pyramids. Introduction, types, characteristic features, structures and function of the following ecosystem:

- (a) Forest ecosystem
- (b) Grassland ecosystem

- (c) Desert ecosystem
 - (d) Aquatic ecosystem (ponds, streams, lakes, rivers, oceans, estuaries).
- (iii) Bio-diversity and its Conservation

Introduction to biodiversity - definition:

Genetic, species and ecosystem diversity, Bio-geographical classification of India, Value of biodiversity: Consumptive use, productive use, social, ethical, aesthetic and option values, Biodiversity at global, national and local levels, India as a mega-diversity nation, Hot-spots of biodiversity, Threats to biodiversity : Habitat loss, Poaching of wildlife, man-wildlife conflicts, rare endangered and threatened species(RET) endemic species of India, method of biodiversity conservation: In-situ and ex-situ conservation.

UNIT-II

[T1], [R3] [No. of hrs. 11]

Natural Resources: problems and prospects

Renewable and Non-renewable Natural Resources; Concept and definition of Natural Resources and need for their management

- **Forest resources:** Use and over-exploitation, deforestation, case studies, timber extraction, mining, dams and their effects on forests and tribal people.
- **Water resources:** Use and over-utilization of surface and ground water, floods, drought, conflicts over water, dams-benefits and problems, Water conservation, rain water harvesting, watershed management.
- **Mineral resources:** Uses are exploitation, environmental effects of extracting and using mineral resources, case studies.
- **Food resources:** World food problems, changes causes by agriculture and over-grazing, effects of modern agriculture, fertilizer-pesticide problems, water logging, salinity, case studies.
- **Energy resources:** Growing energy needs, renewable and non-renewable energy sources, use of alternate energy sources, Urban problems related to energy, case studies.
- **Land resources:** Land as a resource, land degradation, man induced landslides, soil erosion and desertification.

UNIT-III

[T1], [R3] [No. of hrs. 11]

Environmental Chemistry and Pollution Control

(i) Chemistry of Environment

- (a) Green Technology: Principles of Green technology, Zero Waste Technology, Green Chemistry & Its basic principles, Atom Economy, Green Methodologies, clean development mechanisms (CDM), concept of environmental impact assessment,
- (b) Eco-Friendly polymers: Environmental degradation of polymers, Biodegradable, Photo-biodegradable polymers, Hydrolysis &Hydrobiodegradable, Biopolymers &Bioplastics: polylactic acid, polyhydroxybutyrate, polycaprolactone,.Concept of bioremediation.

(ii) Environmental Pollution

Definition, types, causes, effects and control measures of (a) Air pollution, (b) Water pollution, (c) Soil pollution, (d) Marine pollution, (e) Noise pollution, (f) Thermal pollution, (g) Nuclear hazards. Pollution case studies. Solid waste and its management: causes, effects and control measures of urban and industrial waste.

Chemical toxicology-Terms related to toxicity, impact of chemicals (Hg, As, Cd, Cr, Pb) on environment.

UNIT-IV

[T1] [No. of hrs. 11]

Disaster Management, Social Issues, Human Population and the Environment

(i) Disaster Management

Disaster management: floods, earthquake, cyclone and land-slides, nuclear accidents and holocaust, case studies.

(ii) Social Issues, Human Population and the Environment

Sustainable development, Climate change, global warming, acid rain, ozone layer depletion, Environmental ethics: Issues and possible solutions, Consumerism and waste products, Wasteland reclamation. Population growth, problems of urbanisation, Environment Protection Act, 1986; Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981; Water (Prevention and

Control of Pollution) Act, 1974; Wildlife Protection Act, 1972; Forest Conservation Act, 1980; Environmental management, system standards-ISO 14000 series.

Text Book(s):

[T1] E. Barucha, Textbook of Environmental Studies for Undergraduate Courses, Universities Press (India) Pvt. Ltd., 2005.

[T2] S. Chawla, A Textbook of Environmental Studies, McGraw Hill Education Private Limited, 2012

References Books:

[R1] G. T. Miller, Environmental Science, Thomas Learning, 2012

[R2] W. Cunningham and M. A. Cunningham, Principles of Environment Science: Enquiry and Applications, Tata McGraw Hill Publication, N. Delhi, 2003.

[R3] R. Rajagopalan, Environmental Studies: From Crisis to Cure, 2nd Edition, Oxford University Press, 2011.

[R4] A.K. De, Environmental Chemistry, New Age Int. Publ. 2012,,

[R5] A. Kaushik and C.P. Kaushik, Perspectives in Environment Studies, 4th Edition, New Age International Publishers, 2013

[R6] Environmental Engineering by Gerard Kiely, Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd. New Delhi, 2010.

BASIC ELECTRONICS

(Open Elective-II)

Paper Code: ETVEC-506 L T/P C

Paper: Basic Electronics 3 0 3

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be of 12.5 marks.

Objective:

Objective of the paper is to facilitate the student with the basics of electronic aspects that are required for his understanding and applications in their respective field of study. The pre-requisites are, to have a basic understanding of Applied Physics and Mathematics.

UNIT-I

[T1][T2][T3][No. of Hours: 12]

Evaluation of Electronics: Introduction & Application Of Electronics, Energy Band Theory Of Crystals, Energy Band Structures In Metals, Semiconductors And Insulators, Theory Of Semiconductors: Classification Of Semiconductors, Conductivity Of Semiconductors, Carrier Concentration In Intrinsic & Extrinsic Semiconductors, Properties Of Intrinsic And Extrinsic Semiconductors, Variation In Semiconductors Parameters With Temperature, Fermi-Dirac Function, Fermi Level In A Semiconductor Having Impurities, Band Structure Of Open-Circuited P-N Junction, Drift And Diffusion Currents, Carrier Life Time, Continuity Equation (Elementary Treatment Only).

UNIT – II

[T1][T2][T3][No. of Hours: 11]

Theory of p-n Junction Diode: Diode Current Equation, Diode Resistance, Transition Capacitance, Diffusion Capacitance, (Elementary treatment only), Effect of Temperature on p-n Junction Diode, Switching Characteristics, Piecewise Linear Model,

Special Diodes: Zener Diode, Varactor Diode, Tunnel Diode, Photodiode, Light Emitting Diodes, Schottky Barrier Diode,

Applications of Diodes: Half-Wave Diode Rectifier, Full-Wave Rectifier, Clippers and Clampers (Elementary treatment only).

Unit – III

[T1][T2][T3][No. of Hours: 11]

Bipolar Junction Transistor: Introduction of transistor, construction, transistor operations, BJT characteristics, load line, operating point, leakage currents, saturation and cut off mode of operations, Eber-moll's model.

Unit – IV

[T1][T2][T3][No. of Hours: 11]

Application of BJT: CB, CE, CC configurations, hybrid model for transistor at low frequencies, Introduction to FETs and MOSFETs.

Fundamentals of Digital Electronics: Digital and analog signals, number systems, Boolean algebra, logic gates with simple applications, logic gates, karnaugh maps.

UNIT-IV

[T1][T2][No. of Hrs. 11]

Band Theory of Solids: Introduction, Kronig-Penney model: E-k diagram, Effective mass of an electron, Intrinsic semiconductors: Electron concentration in conduction band, Hole concentration in valence band, Extrinsic semiconductor: p-type and n-type semiconductors, Fermi level, Hall Effect: Hall voltage and Hall coefficient.

Text Book(s):

[T1] Arthur Beiser, 'Concepts of Modern Physics', [McGraw-Hill], 6th Edition 2009

[T2] A. S. Vasudeva, 'Modern Engineering Physics', S. Chand, 6th Edition, 2013.

Reference Book(s):

[R1] A. Ghatak 'Optics', TMH, 5th Edition, 2013

[R2] G. Aruldas 'Engineering Physics' PHI 1st Edition, 2010.

[R3] Feynman "The Feynman lectures on Physics Pearson Volume 3 Millennium Edition, 2013

[R4] Uma Mukhrji 'Engineering Physics' Narosa, 3rd Edition, 2010.

[R5] H.K. Malik & A. K. Singh 'Engineering Physics' [McGraw-Hill], 1st Edition, 2009.

BASICS OF ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING

(Open Elective-II)

Paper Code: ETVEE-508 L T/P C

Paper: Basics of Electrical Engineering 3 0 3

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS: 75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be of 12.5 marks.

Objective: To provide exposure to the students in respects of the basics of different aspects of electrical engineering with emphasis on constructional, measurement and applications of various types of instruments and equipments.

UNIT – I: DC Circuits

[T1],[T2][No. of Hrs. 11]

Introduction of Circuit parameters and energy sources (Dependent and Independent), Mesh and Nodal Analysis, Superposition, Thevenin's, Norton's, Reciprocity, Maximum Power Transfer and Millman's Theorems, Star-Delta Transformation and their Applications to the Analysis of DC circuits.

UNIT – II: A.C.Circuits

[T1],[T2][No. of Hrs. 14]

A.C. Fundamentals, Phasor representation, Steady State Response of Series and Parallel R-L, R-C and R-L-C circuits using j-notation, Series and Parallel resonance of RLC Circuits, Quality factor, Bandwidth, Complex Power, Introduction to balanced 3-phase circuits with Star- Delta Connections.

UNIT – III: Measuring Instruments

[T1],[T2],[R2][No. of Hrs. 11]

Basics of measuring instruments and their types ,Working principles and applications of moving coil, moving iron (ammeter & voltmeter) and Extension of their ranges, dynamometer- type Wattmeter , induction-type Energy Meter , Two-wattmeter method for the measurement of power in three phase circuits, Introduction to digital voltmeter, digital Multimeter and Electronic Energy Meter.

UNIT – IV: Transformer and Rotating Machines

[T1],[T2],[R2][No. of Hrs. 12]

Fundamentals of Magnetic Circuits, Hysteresis and Eddy current losses, working principle, equivalent circuit, efficiency and voltage regulation of single phase transformer and its applications. Introduction to DC and Induction motors (both three phase and single phase), Stepper Motor and Permanent Magnet Brushless DC Motor.

Text Books:

[T1] S.N Singh, “Basic Electrical Engineering” PHI India Ed 2012

[T2] Chakrabarti, Chanda,Nath “Basic Electrical Engineering” TMH India”, Ed 2012.

Reference Books:

[R1] William Hayt “Engineering Circuit Analysis” TMH India Ed 2012

[R2] Giorgio Rizzoni “Principles and Application of Electrical Engineering” Fifth Edition TMH India.

ENGINEERING MATERIALS**(Open Elective-II)**

Paper Code: ETVME-510 L T/P C

Paper: Engineering Materials 3 0 3

INSTRUCTIONS TO PAPER SETTERS:

MAXIMUM MARKS:

75

1. Question No. 1 should be compulsory and cover the entire syllabus. This question should have objective or short answer type questions. It should be of 25 marks.
2. Apart from Question No. 1, rest of the paper shall consist of four units as per the syllabus. Every unit should have two questions. However, student may be asked to attempt only 1 question from each unit. Each question should be 12.5 marks.

Objectives and Pre-requisites:

To acquire proper knowledge about different construction materials and their applications. To have exposure about various construction materials as required in engineering. The students should learn the details of various construction materials such as stones, bricks and tiles, cement and cement based products, and lime, timber and wood based products, paint and varnishes metals and other miscellaneous materials and their applications.

Learning outcomes:

Helps in making him as a better supervisor at construction sites/ industries. Improved ability to identify and visualize various construction materials that are being used in construction and other industries. Enhanced knowledge of construction materials helps students in pursuing

their careers in material testing field. This subject helps in understanding the various subjects related to different vocational courses in later stages.

UNIT-I:

Building Stones:

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Classification of Rocks, Geological classification: Igneous, sedimentary and metamorphic rocks. Chemical classification: Calcareous, argillaceous and siliceous rocks. Physical classification: Un-stratified, stratified and foliated rocks; Requirements of good building stones, testing & identification of common building stones and their uses. Bricks and Tiles: Introduction to bricks, Raw materials for brick manufacturing and properties of good brick making earth, Classification of bricks as per IS: 1077, Testing of common building bricks as per IS: 3495. Compressive strength, water absorption, efflorescence test, Dimensional tolerance test. Types and use of- tiles for wall, roofing & flooring; ceramic tiles; Hollow masonry blocks; Fly ash bricks.

UNIT-II:

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 11]

Cement: Introduction, raw materials, manufacturing of ordinary Portland cement, flow diagram for wet and dry process. Properties and uses of ordinary Portland cement. Special cements and their uses. Storage of cement. Lime:-Introduction: Lime as one of the cementing materials. Definition of terms; quick lime, fat lime, hydraulic lime, hydrated lime, lump lime. Calcinations and slaking of lime IS classification of lime. Definition- Properties and uses of Mortar. Types of mortar, cement & lime Mortar, Preparation of cement Mortar.

UNIT III:

[T1, T2][No. of Hrs: 10]

Timber and wood based products. Identification of different types of timber: Teak, Deodar, Shisham, Sal, Mango. Market forms of converted timber as per IS. Seasoning of timber: purpose, methods of seasoning. Defects and decay in timber, Preservation of timber and methods of treatment, Properties and specifications of structural timber. Other wood based products, their brief description of manufacture and uses: Lamina board, Black board, fiber board. Hard board and gypsum board.

UNIT IV:

[T1, T2][No. of Hours: 12]

Purpose and use of paints, Types, ingredients, properties and uses of oil paints, water paints and Cement paints. Types, properties and uses of varnishes, Trade name of different products. Metals: - uses of ferrous and non- ferrous metals, Commercial forms of ferrous and non-ferrous metals. Plastics – Introduction and uses of various plastic products in buildings such as doors, water tanks and PVC pipes. Types uses and application of- Fiber Sheets, insulating materials, Materials used in interior decoration works like POP, Water proofing compounds, fire resisting materials.

Text Book(s):

[T1] Surendra Singh; “Engineering Materials; “New Delhi”.Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.

[T2] TTTI, Chandigarh “Civil Engineering Materials; “Tata McGraw Hill.

Reference Book(s):

- [R1] M.L.Gambhir and NehaJamwal, “Building Materials”, Tata McGraw Hill.
- [R2] Building Materials, P.C.Varghese, PHI Publications
- [R3] Engineering materials S.C. Rangwala, Charotar Publishing House
- [R4] Building Materials, Duggal, New Age Publication
- [R5] Kulkarni, GJ; “Engineering Materials; “Ahmedabad, Ahmedabad Book Depot.

BASIC ELECTRONICS LAB

Paper Code: ETVEC-556

L T/P C

Paper: Basic Electronics Lab 0 2 2

List of Experiments:

1. Introduction to C.R.O, Function Generator& Bread Board Kit & to generate different types of waveform with the help of Function Generator & to calculate their frequency, amplitude AC & DC voltage.
2. Identification & testing of Active & passive components
3. To plot V-I characteristics of a semiconductor diode & Calculate Static & Dynamic Resistance
4. To Study the Reverse characteristics of Zener diode
5. To Study the Rectifier circuit.
 - a) Half Wave Rectifier
 - b) Centre Tapped Rectifier.
 - c) Bridge Rectifier.
6. To Study the output waveforms of different Filter Ckts of Rectifier.
7. To Plot Input & Output characteristics CB transistor.
8. To Plot Input & Output characteristics of CE transistor.
9. Realization of basic gates.
10. Implementation of Boolean functions (two or three variables).
11. Few experiments mentioned above to be performed on P-spice.
12. To develop a working model of any electronic circuit.

Note:- Any 8-10 Experiments out of the list may be chosen.

APPLIED PHYSICS LAB

Paper Code: ETVPH-552 L T/P C

Paper: Applied Physics Lab 0 2 2

List of Experiments:

Instructions: Twelve Experiments are to be chosen from the list given below and rest of the Experiments (i.e., three in number) may be designed by the faculty at the respective institute according to the Syllabus being taught.

1. To determine the wavelength of sodium light by Newton's Rings.
2. To determine the wavelength of sodium light by Fresnel's biprism.
3. To determine the wavelength of sodium light using diffraction grating.
4. To measure small thickness of a piece of paper using Newton's Rings technique.
5. To determine the refractive index of a prism using spectrometer.
6. To determine the dispersive power of prism using spectrometer and mercury source.
7. To determine the specific rotation of cane sugar solution with the help of half shade polarimeter.
8. To find the wavelength of He-Ne laser using transmission diffraction grating.
9. To determine the numeral aperture (NA) of an optical fibre.
10. To determine the e/m ratio of an electron by J.J. Thomson method.
11. To measure time period of a waveform and calculate its frequency and wavelength using CRO.
12. To measure the frequency of a sine-wave voltage obtained from signal generator and to obtain lissajous pattern on the CRO screen by feeding two sine wave signals from two signal generators.
13. To determine the frequency of A.C. mains by using Sonometer .
14. To determine the frequency of electrically maintained tuning fork by Melde's method.
15. Computer simulation (simple application of Monte Carlo): Brownian motion, charging & discharging of a capacitor.
16. To study the charging and discharging of a capacitor and to find out the time constant.
17. To study the Hall effect.
18. To determine the energy band gap of a semiconductor by four probe method/or by measuring the variation of reverse saturation current with temperature.
19. To study the V-I characteristics of Zener diode.
20. To measure surface tension of different liquids using capillary rise method.
21. To measure coefficient of viscosity by Stoke's method.

Text Book(s):

[T1] C. L. Arora 'B. Sc. Practical Physics' S. Chand

BASICS OF ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING LAB

Paper Code: ETVEE-558 L T/P C

Paper: Basics of Electrical Engineering 0 2 2

List of Experiments:

1. To Design the circuit for a given load and selection of its various Components and instruments from the safety point of view
 2. Study and applications of CRO for measurement of voltage, frequency and phase of signals.
 3. Connection of lamp by
 - (1) Single Switch Method.
 - (2) Two-way Switch Method.
- OR
- Performance comparison of of fluorescent Tube & CFL Lamp.
4. To Verify Thevenin's & Norton's Theorem
- OR To Verify Superposition & Reciprocity Theorem.
- OR To Verify Maximum Power Transfer Theorem.
5. To Measure Power & Power Factor in a Single-Phase A.C Circuit using Three Ammeters or three Voltmeters.
 6. To Measure Power & Power Factor in a Balanced Three Phase Circuit using Two Single Phase Wattmeters.
 7. To study of Resonance in a series R-L-C or Parallel R-L-C Circuits.
 8. To perform open circuit and short circuit test on 1-phase transformer.
 9. Starting, Reversing and speed control of DC shunt Motor
 10. Starting, Reversing and speed control of 3-phase Induction Motor
 11. To Study different types of Storage Batteries & its charging system.
 12. To Study different types of earthing methods including earth leakage circuit breaker (GFCI)

Note:- Any 8-10 Experiments out of the list may be chosen.

ENGINEERING MATERIALS LAB

Paper Code: ETVME-560 L T/P C

Paper: Engineering Materials Lab 0 2 2

List of Experiments:

- 1) To determine the crushing strength of bricks
- 2) To determine the water absorption of bricks.
- 3) To conduct field tests on cement.
- 4) To determine fineness (by sieve method) of cement.
- 5) To determine normal consistency of cement.

- 6) To determine initial and final setting times of cement.
- 7) To determine soundness of cement.
- 8) To determine compressive strength of cement.
- 9) Field visit to study different types of cements that are used in construction industry
- 10) Field visit to study different types of bricks that are used in construction
- 11) Field visit to study use of timber in construction
- 12) A report on use of plastic materials for various purposes in buildings
- 13) Field visit to study different types of tiles used in construction industry
- 14) Field visit to study different type of paints used in buildings
- 15) A report on new and latest material being used in construction industry.

Teachers are expected to physically show various materials while imparting instructions. Field visits should be organized and active participation of students shall be encouraged.

CIVIL ENGINEERING DRAWING LAB

Paper Code: ETVCT-552 L T/P C

Paper: Civil Engineering Drawing Lab 0 4 4

Objectives and Pre-requisites:

Drawing is the language of engineers and technicians. To Read and interpret engineering drawing as required in their day-to-day responsibility. The pre requisite knowledge on building components and construction is necessary. The course is aimed at developing basic graphic skills so as to enable them to use these skills in preparation of engineering drawings, their reading and interpretation.

Learning outcomes:

Able to draw the plan of different components and fixtures of buildings. Capable of preparing plans, sections and elevations of different engineering units as per requirements. Improves the ability to think and work in accordance with the client/ project requirements and needs. This subject helps in better understanding of the concepts of CAD in later stages of the course.

DETAILED CONTENTS

1. Drawing of different conventions for materials in section, conventional breaks for shafts, pipes, rectangular, square, angle, channel, rolled sections
2. Elevation, sectional plan and sectional side elevation of flush door & glazed door
3. Elevation, section plan and sectional side elevation of paneled window and glazed window
4. Details of spread footing foundations, load bearing and non-load bearing wall for given thickness of walls with the help of given data or rule of the thumb, showing offsets, position of DPC. The details of the concrete and brick plinth protection have to be shown in the drawing.

5. Plans of 'T' and Corner junction of walls of 1 Brick, 1-1/2 Brick and 2 brick thick in English bond
6. Wooden roof truss showing details of joints, fixation of roof coverings, eaves and gutters- King post truss
7. Wooden roof truss showing details of joints, fixation of roof coverings, eaves and gutters- queen post truss
8. Drawing plan and section of a dog legged stair (excluding reinforcement details)
9. Drawing plan, elevation of a small building by measurement.
10. Drawing detailed plan, elevation and section of a two room residential building from a given line plan, showing details of foundations, roof and parapet
11. Drawing of a small single storey building showing position of sanitary fittings house drainage and electrical fittings
12. Drawing of floors (concrete flooring, ceramic/vitrified tile flooring)
13. Drawing details of damp proofing arrangement of roofs, basement floors and walls as per BIS Code
14. Drawing the plan and elevation of an office building
15. Drawing the plan and elevation of primary health care centre
16. Drawing the plan and elevation of post office

ESTIMATING & COSTING LAB

Paper Code: ETVCT-554 L T/P C

Paper: Estimating & Costing Lab 0 2 2

List of Experiments:

- A. Detailed estimate for building taking of quantities for all items of works in the following types of building:
 - 1) A small residential building with two / three rooms with RCC roofs.
 - 2) Two storied building (frame structure) with RCC roofs.
 - 3) Cottages with sloped RCC roofs.
 - 4) Industrial buildings with AC / GI sheet roof with steel trusses.
 - 5) Community hall with columns and T-Beams.
 - 6) Open well with masonry steining.
 - 7) Septic tanks with dispersion trench / soak pit.
 - 8) R.C.C. slab culvert.
 - 9) Pipe culvert
 - 10) Water bound Macadam Road
 - 11) Rain water systems in the buildings
 - a. Shallow well
 - b. Percolation Pit with bore.

- B. Rate analysis for following item of works.
 - a. Brick work for super structures.
 - b. PCC work for footing.
 - c. RCC work for beam. Column and slabs.
 - d. Plaster work
 - e. White/ Colour washing
- C. Taking out quantities for embankment and canals

INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY

This is an applied engineering subject. Teachers are expected to provide working drawings for various civil engineering works and students be asked to calculate the quantities of materials required for execution of such works. Teachers should conceptualize analysis of rates for different types of works along with valuation of property.

ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE LAB/ FIELD WORK

(Common to All Disciplines)

Paper Code: ETVEN-552 L T/P C

Paper: Environmental Science Lab/ Field Work 0 2 2

List of Experiments

1. Determination of pH, conductivity and turbidity in drinking water sample.
2. Determination of pH and conductivity of soil/sludge samples.
3. Determination of moisture content of soil sample.
4. Determination of Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) of water sample.
5. Determination of dissolved oxygen (DO) in the water sample.
6. Determination of Biological oxygen demand (BOD) in the water sample.
7. Determination of Chemical oxygen demand (COD) in the water sample.
8. Determination of Residual Chlorine in the water sample.
9. Determination of ammonia in the water sample.
10. Determination of carbon dioxide in the water sample.
11. Determination of nitrate ions or sulphate ions in water using spectrophotometer.
12. Determination of the molecular weight of polystyrene sample using viscometer method.
13. Base catalyzed aldol condensation by Green Methodology.
14. Acetylation of primary amines using eco-friendly method.
15. To determine the concentration of particulate matter in the ambient air using High Volume Sampler.

P.S.: For better understanding of various aspects of environment visits to local areas, depending upon easy access and importance may be planned to any nearby river, forest, grassland, hills and students should write a report based on their observations.

Suggested Books:

- [T1] A. I. Vogel, G. H. Jeffery, Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis, Published by Longman Scientific & Technical, 5th Edition, 1989.
- [T2] dst.gov.in/green-chem.pdf (monograph of green chemistry laboratory experiments).
- [T3] S. Chawla, Essentials of Experimental Engineering Chemistry, DhanpatRai & Co., 3rd Edition, 2008.
- [T4] S. Rattan, Experiments in Applied Chemistry, Published by S.K. Kataria & Sons, 2nd Edition, 2003.
- [T5] W. Cunningham and M. A. Cunningham, Principles of Environment Science: Enquiry and Applications, Tata McGraw Hill Publication, N. Delhi, 2003.
- [T6] A. Kaushik and C. P. Kaushik, Perspectives in Environment Studies, 4th Edition, New Age International Publishers, 2013.

PROJECT-I

Paper Code: ETVCT-556 L T/P C

Paper: Project-I 033

Objectives:

The practical training cum project work is intended to place students for project oriented practical training in actual work situations for the stipulated period with a view to:

- a) Develop understanding regarding the size and scale of operations and nature of field work in which students are going to play their role after completing the courses of study.
- b) Develop understanding of subject based knowledge given in the class room in the context of its application at work places
- c) Develop first-hand experience and confidence amongst the students to enable them to use and apply polytechnic/institute based knowledge and skills to solve practical problems in the world of work.
- d) Develop special skills and abilities like interpersonal skills, communication skills, attitudes and values.

This practical training cum project work should not be considered as merely conventional industrial training in which students are sent at work places with minimal supervision. This experience is required to be planned and supervised on regular basis by the polytechnic faculty. For the fulfilment of above objectives, polytechnic may establish close linkage with 8-10 relevant organization for providing such an experience. It is necessary that each organization is visited well in advance and activities to be performed by student are well defined. The chosen activities should be such which are of curricular interest to students and of professional value to industrial/field organizations. Each teacher is expected to supervise and guide 5-6 students. Effort should be made to identify actual field problems to be given as project work to the students. Project selected should not be too complex which is beyond the level of the students. The placement of the students for such a practical cum project work should match with the competency profile of students and the project work assigned to them. Students may be assessed both by industry and polytechnic faculty.

VOCATION WORKSHOP-II

Paper Code: ETVCT-562 L T/P C

Paper: Vocation Workshop-II 0 4 4

Objectives and Pre-requisites:

To have a balanced overall development of student; To integrate theory with practice; To provide hand on experience about use of different tools and basic manufacturing practices; To develop general manual and machining skills in the students.

Learning outcomes: Students are able to respect and visualize dignity of labour, precision, safety at work place, team working and development of right attitude.

DETAILED CONTENTS (PRACTICAL EXERCISES)

Note: The students are supposed to come in proper workshop dress prescribed by the institute. Wearing shoes in the workshop(s) is compulsory. Importance of safety and cleanliness, safety measures and upkeep of tools, equipment and environment in each of the following shops should be explained and practiced. The students should prepare sketches of various tools/jobs in their practical Notebook.

Sheet Metal Shop

1. Shearing and riveting practice on G.I.
2. Practice on making single riveted lap joint/double riveted lap Joint.
3. Practice on making single cover plate chain type, seam joint and riveted butt joint

Smithy Shop

1. Job work to forge a L-hook.
2. Job work to prepare a job involving upsetting process
3. Job work to forge a chisel
4. Job work to prepare a cube from a M.S. round by forging method.

Electrical shop

1. Use of Megger for testing wiring
2. Study of protection devices- fuse, MCB, ELCB/RCCB etc
3. Measurement of earth resistance
4. Study of various home appliances
5. Study of different types of earthing
6. Field visit to electrical substation- indoor/ outdoor
7. Study and hands on training on single and three phase induction motor
8. Study of firefighting equipment

References Books:

- [R1] Workshop Technology I,II,III, by S K Hajra, Choudhary and A K Chaoudhary; Media Promoters and Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Bombay
- [R2] Workshop Technology by Manchanda Vol. I,II,III; India Publishing House, Jalandhar.
- [R3] Manual on Workshop Practice by K Venkata Reddy, KL Narayana et al; MacMillan India Ltd. New Delhi

- [R4] Basic Workshop Practice Manual by T Jeyapoovan; Vikas Publishing House (P) Ltd., New Delhi
- [R5] Workshop Technology by B.S. Raghuwansh;,DhanpatRai and Co., New Delh
- [R6] Workshop Technology by HS Bawa; Tata McGraw Hill Publishers, New Delhi

Annex-1
B. Tech. in
Construction Technology
Course Structure
2020-21

B. Tech. in Construction Technology

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester I		Applied Mathematics I	1	1	1	1	4
		Applied Chemistry	2	0	1	1	4
		Construction Engineering Fundamentals	2	0	1	1	4
		Computer Programming	1	0	1	1	3
		Engineering Drawing	0	0	1	3	4
		IDSC-I (Life Coping Skills)	0	0	0	3	3
		Environmental Studies	2	0	0	1	3
		Total Credits					25
Semester II		Applied Mathematics II	1	1	1	1	4
		Applied Physics	2	0	1	1	4
		Basic of Electrical and Electronics Engineering	1	0	1	1	3
		Material Science and Engineering	2	0	1	1	4
		Construction Materials-I	1	0	1	1	3
		Workshop Practice (Lab)	0	0	1	2	3
		IDSC-2 (Life Coping Skills)	0	0	0	3	3
		Internship-I	0	0	0	0	8
		Total Credits					32
Semester	Subject	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credit

											s
	Code										
Semester III		Applied Mathematics III	1	1		1			1		4
		Engineering Mechanics	2	0		1			1		4
		Structural Analysis	2	1		0			1		4
		Computer Aided Building Drawing	0	0		1			1		2
		Construction Materials-II	2	0		1			1		4
		Fluid Mechanics	1	0		1			1		3
		Construction Methods & Planning	1	0		1			1		3
		IDSC-3 (Life Coping Skills)	0	0		0			3		3
		Total Credits									27
Semester IV		Strength of Materials	1	0		1			1		3
		Concrete technology	2	0		1			1		4
		Quantity surveying & evaluation	2	0		1			1		4
		Geotechnical Engineering	1	1		1			1		4
		Surveying-I	1	0		1			1		3
		Planning & Scheduling Lab	0	0		1			1		2
		IDSC-4 (Life Coping Skills)				0	0	0		3	3
		Internship-II							-		8
		Total Credits									31

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester		Engineering Geology &	1	1	1	1	4

V		Rock Mechanics					
		Tendering and Contracting	2	0	1	1	4
		Construction Safety & Material Handling	1	0	1	1	3
		Theory of Structures	2	1	0	1	4
		Theory of structures	2	1	0	1	4
		Elective I Subject					
		Building Maintenance and Repairs	1	1	1	1	4
		Advanced Project Planning					
		Construction Logistics					
		IDSC-5 (Life Coping Skills)	0	0	0	3	3
		Disaster Management					
Semester VI		Design of Steel Structures	2	1	0	1	4
		Water Resource Management	1	1	1	1	4
		Civil, Tax laws and Contrast laws	1	1	2	2	4
		Environmental Engineering	2	0	1	1	4
		Elective II Subject					
		Energy Management	1	1	1	1	4
		Procurement and Resource Management					
		Transport Infrastructure					
		IDSC-6 (Life Coping Skill)	0	0	0	3	3
		Internship-III	-				8

	Total Credits	31
--	---------------	----

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester VII		Internship-IV			-		13
		Seminar			-		2
		Total Credits					15

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester VIII		Internship-IV			-		13
		Seminar			-		2
		Total Credits	15				
Semester VIII		Reinforced Concrete Design	1	1	0	1	4
		Foundation Engineering	1	1	1	1	4
		Elective III Subject					
		MEP	1	1	1	1	4

		Environment, Health and Safety Management	1	1	1	1	4
		Hydro Infrastructure	1	1	1	1	4
		Project					13
		Seminar					2
		IDSC-7 (Life Coping Skill)	0	0	0	3	3
							30

Annex-II
Madan Bhandari Technological University
B. Tech. in
Construction Technology
Reviewed Course Structure
2020-21

Course Structure of B. Tech. in Construction Technology

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester I		Applied Mathematics I	1	1	1	1	4
		Applied Chemistry	2	0	1	1	4
		Construction Engineering Fundamentals	2	0	1	1	4
		Computer Programming	1	0	1	1	3
		Engineering Drawing	0	0	1	3	4
		IDSC-I (Life Coping Skills)	0	0	0	3	3
		Environmental Studies	2	0	0	1	3
		Total Credits					25
Semester II		Applied Mathematics II	1	1	1	1	4
		Applied Physics	2	0	1	1	4
		Basic of Electrical and Electronics Engineering	1	0	1	1	3
		Material Science and Engineering	2	0	1	1	4
		Construction Materials-I	1	0	1	1	3
		Workshop Practice (Lab)	0	0	1	2	3
		IDSC-2 (Life Coping Skills)	0	0	0	3	3
		Internship-I	0	0	0	0	8
		Total Credits					32

Course Structure of B. Tech. in Construction Technology

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester III		Applied Mathematics III	1	1	1	1	4
		Engineering Mechanics	2	0	1	1	4
		Structural Analysis	2	1	0	1	4
		Computer Aided Building Drawing	0	0	1	1	2

		Construction Materials-II	2	0	1	1	4
		Fluid Mechanics	1	0	1	1	3
		Construction Methods & Planning	1	0	1	1	3
		IDSC-3 (Life Coping Skills)	0	0	0	3	3
		Total Credits					27
Semester IV		Strength of Materials	1	0	1	1	3
		Concrete technology	2	0	1	1	4
		Quantity surveying & evaluation	2	0	1	1	4
		Geotechnical Engineering	1	1	1	1	4
		Surveying-I	1	0	1	1	3
		Planning & Scheduling Lab	0	0	1	1	2
		IDSC-4 (Life Coping Skills)	0	0	0	3	3
		Internship-II			-		8
		Total Credits					31

Course Structure of B. Tech. in Construction Technology

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester V		Engineering Geology & Rock Mechanics	1	1	1	1	4
		Tendering and Contracting	2	0	1	1	4
		Construction Safety & Material Handling	1	0	1	1	3
		Theory of Structures	2	1	0	1	4
		Theory of structures	2	1	0	1	4
		Elective I Subject					
		Building Maintenance and Repairs	1	1	1	1	4
		Advanced Project Planning					
		Construction Logistics					
		IDSC-5 (Life Coping Skills)	0	0	0	3	3

		Disaster Management					
Semester VI		Design of Steel Structures	2	1	0	1	4
		Water Resource Management	1	1	1	1	4
		Civil, Tax laws and Contrast laws	1	1	2	2	4
		Environmental Engineering	2	0	1	1	4
		Elective II Subject					
		Energy Management	1	1	1	1	4
		Procurement and Resource Management					
		Transport Infrastructure					
		IDSC-6 (Life Coping Skill)	0	0	0	3	3
		Internship-III	-				8
		Total Credits					31

Course Structure of B. Tech. in Construction Technology

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester VII		Internship-IV			-		13
		Seminar			-		2
		Total Credits					15

Semester	Subject Code	Subject Name	L	T	P	S	Credits
Semester VIII		Internship-IV			-		13
		Seminar			-		2

		Total Credits	15				
Semester VIII	CNST 405	Reinforced Concrete Design	1	1	0	1	4
	CNST 404	Foundation Engineering	1	1	1	1	4
		Elective III Subject					
	CNST 405	MEP	1	1	1	1	4
	CNST 406	Environment, Health and Safety Management	1	1	1	1	4
	CNST 407	Hydro Infrastructure	1	1	1	1	4
	CNST 408	Project					13
	CNST 409	Seminar					2
	IDSC 402	IDSC-7 (Life Coping Skill)	0	0	0	3	3
	Total Credits						30

Annex-III

B.Tech - Mechatronics Engineering

(Bachelor of Technology- Mechatronics Engineering)

Reviewed Structure of B. Tech

(Mechatronics Engineering)- Semester-I

S.No	Course Code	Course Name	Hours												Credits		
			C	L	T	P	S	H	L	T	P	S	C				
1	APSC101	Applied	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	4			
		Mathematics I															
2	APSC102	Applied physics	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4				
3	ENGG104	Applied	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4				
		Thermodynamics															
4	ENGG102	Computer	3	1	0	2	1	4	1	0	1	1	3				
		Programming															
5	ENGG105	Basics of Electrical	3	1	0	2	1	4	1	0	1	1	3				
		and Electronics															

6	IDCS101	IDSC-I	3	0	0	0		3	3	0	0		0	3	3	
7	IEVS100	Environmental	3	2				1	3	2				1	3	
			2	9	1	10		9	29	9	1		5	8	24	
			4													
		Semester-II														
Sr	Course Code	Course Name					Hours				Credits					
No																
			C	C	T	P	S	H	L	T		P	S	C		
				L												
1	APSC104	Applied	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1		1	1	4		
		Mathematics II														
2	APSC103	Applied	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0		1	1	4		
3	ENGG101	Engineering	4	0	0	2	3	5	0	0		1	3	4		
4	ENGG106	Material Science	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0		1	1	4		
		and Engineering														
		Mechatronics														
5	MTRX101	Engineering	3	1	0	2	1	4	1	0		1	1	3		
		Fundamentals														

6	ENGG108	Workshop	3	0	0	2		2	4	0	0		1	2	3
7	IDSC102	IDSC-2(life coping)	3	0	0	0		3	3	0	0		0	3	3
8	MTRX102	Internship	8												8
			3	6	1	12		1	31	6	1		6	12	33
			3					2							

Reviewed Structure of B. Tech (Mechatronics Engineering) Semester-III

Sr No	Course Code	Course Name	Hours									Credits		
			C	CL	T	P	S	H	L	T	P	S	C	
1	APSC201	Applied Mathematics III	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	4
2	MTRX201	Analog and Digital Electronics	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4	
3	AUTO202	Manufacturing Technology	3	1	0	2	1	4	1	0	1	1	3	
4	ENGG103	Engineering Mechanics	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4	

5	ENGG204	Fluid Mechanics		3	1	0	2	1	4	1	0	1	1	3
6	MTRX202	Matlab and Simulink		3	0	0	2	2	4	0	0	1	2	3
7	IDSC201	IDSC-3(life coping skill)		3	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	3	3
				24	7	1	1	1	3	7	1	6	11	2
				Semester-IV										
Sr	Course Code	Course Name		Hours							Credits			
No														
				C	C	T	P	S	H	L	T	P	S	C
1	MTRX203	Control Engineering		4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4
2	ENGG202	Computer Aided Design		3	0	0	2	2	4	0	0	1	2	3
3	ENGG107	Strength of Materials		3	1	0	2	1	4	1	0	1	1	3
4	MTRX205	Microprocessor and Application Electronic		4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4

5	MTRX204	Measurements and Instrumentation	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4
6	ENGG201	Heat and Mass transfer	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4
7	IDSC202	IDSC-4(life coping skill)	3	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	3	3
8	MTRX207	Internship	8										8
			33	7	2	12	10	31	7	2	6	10	33

Reviewed Structure of B. Tech (Mechatronics Engineering) Semester-V

Sr No	Course Code	Course Name	Hours							Credits				
			C	CL	T	P	S	H	L	T	P	S	C	
1	MTRX301	Industrial Robotics	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4	
2	MTRX302	Communication Systems	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4	
3	MTRX303	Power Electronics and Drives	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4	
4	MTRX206	Digital Signal Processing	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4	
5	AUTO201	Theory of Mechanism	3	1	0	2	1	4	1	0	1	1	3	

6	MTRX305/06 /07	Elective-I 1. Process Automation 2. Automotive Electronics 3. Computer Integrated Manufacturing	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4
7	IDSC301	IDSC-5(life coping skill)	3	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	3	3
	Audit Corse	Disaster Management											
			26	7	3	10	8	32	9	2	6	9	26

**Semester-
VI**

Sr No	Course Code	Course Name	Hours							Credits				
			C	CL	T	P	S	H	L	T	P	S	C	
1	MTRX308	Industrial Automation	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4	
2	MTRX309	Mechatronics System Design	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4	
3	MTRX314	Renewable Energy System	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4	
4	ENGG203	Dynamics of Machinery	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4	
5	MTRX311	Product Development	4	2	0	2	1	5	2	0	1	1	4	

6	Elective-II MTRX312 AUTO309	1.Mechatronicin Medical Applications 2. Hybrid and Electric Vehicle 3. Rapid Prototyping	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4
	MTRX313												
7	IDSC302	IDSC-6(life coping skill)	3	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	3	3
8	MTRX317	Internship	8										8
			35	8	4	12	9	33	8	4	6	9	35

Reviewed Structure of B. Tech (Mechatronics Engineering) Semester-VII

Sr No	Course Code	Course Name	Hours										Credits		
			C	CL	T	P	S	H	L	T	P	S	C		
1	MTRX401	Internship	13											13	
2	MTRX402	Seminar	2											2	
			15											15	
Semester-VIII															
Sr No	Course Code	Course Name	Hours										Credits		

			C	CL	T	P	S	H	L	T	P	S	C
1	MTRX304	Internet of Things	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4
2	ENGG301	Reliability Engineering	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4
3	Elective-III MTRX310/15/16	1) Digital Hardware Design and Analysis 2) Building Automation 3) Total Quality Management	4	1	1	2	1	5	1	1	1	1	4
4	MTRX403	Project	13										13
5	MTRX404	Seminar	2										2
6	IDSC401	IDSC-7 [Life Coping Skills]	3	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	3	3
			30	3	3	6	6	18	3	3	3	3	30

24+33+24+33+26+35+15+30

Total credits: 220